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About WGNE

The Working Group on Numerical Experimentation (WGNE) to foster collaborative development of models of the Earth system (design, implementation, error diagnosis and model revision) across the full range of temporal and spatial scales. WGNE contributes to the mission of the WCRP core project ESMO.

About ESMO

The Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) core project coordinates, advances, and facilitates all modelling, data assimilation and observational activities within WCRP. Website: wcrp-esmo.org

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A | Notes from the Editors

From the Editor,

Earth System Modeling and Numerical Experimentation are advancing at a significant rate. The use of newer and emerging technologies is moving the field forward, either directly through novel methodologies or through associated growth in existing areas such as coupling, forcing response, parameterization, and verification. We are pleased to present a collection of articles describing such developments and research in this publication.

This publication, “Research Activities in Earth System Modelling,” often referred to as the “WGNE Bluebook,” has been a longstanding activity carried out by the WCRP Working Group on Numerical Experimentation (WGNE) since 1970. When WGNE joined the WCRP core project Earth System Modelling and Observation (ESMO), it was decided that the ESMO IPO would assume editorial and publication responsibility for the Bluebook. After a successful first year, we are pleased to publish the second WGNE Bluebook under ESMO’s stewardship and continue to fulfill the publication’s original intention: to provide an accessible avenue for information exchange among modeling researchers.

Remarkably, this year marks the 40th anniversary of WGNE’s formation as a working group, initially under the joint supervision of the Commission for Atmospheric Sciences and the World Climate Research Programme and later reporting to the WMO Research Board. The technological progress and transformations over these four decades are immense and this publication stands as a testament to the work of thousands of scientists and researchers who continuously advance the field.

Producing this publication required the contributions of many individuals. I would like to thank the panel members of WGNE and Dr. Fanny Adloff for their careful review of the articles. Special thanks go to Sara Pasqualetto for her excellent work on the design and formatting of the final book. Last but not least, I extend my gratitude to all the authors who contributed to this collection. Through the research published in this volume, their work will inform and inspire many others to pursue further research and development in Earth System Modelling.

Sincerely,

Dr. Bimochan Niraula

Scientific Officer,

WCRP Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) International Project Office

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Development and studies of coupled models and Earth System Models

Generic Co-processing for Earth System Models: An Implementation within the Unified Forecast System Weather Model (UFS-WM)

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1. Introduction

As the complexity of the earth system modeling applications increases significantly in terms of represented physical processes and their nonlinear interactions, our ability to process and interact with the vast amount of data produced by those applications is fundamentally changed and pushed the community to develop new and novel data processing approaches such as co-processing and in situ visualization. The Unified Forecast System Weather Model (UFS-WM; Worthen et al., 2024) is one of the real examples of such a complex, multi-component modeling system that aims to replace existing NOAA's operational model suite and applications by unifying different modeling applications and configurations. The main objective of this study is to increase interoperability between Earth system models and novel data-processing tools by providing an easy-to-use, efficient, and standardized modeling environment for interacting with large data. The newly developed data processing component (GeoGate) interacts with any ESMF/NUOPC-based model component to bring co-processing capability and allow gaining insight from data flowing from multiple Earth system model components and using it to make timely, data-driven decisions. The NUOPC Layer mainly defines conventions and a set of generic components for building coupled models using the Earth System Modeling Framework (ESMF; Theurich et al., 2016). The new component is initially integrated with the UFS Coastal modeling system and currently testing to support model development efforts as a part of the existing regression testing (RT) framework. In addition, its plugin-based design enables it to extend its functionality such as Interacting with different programming languages (i.e. Python) to process the data, and having online interaction with AI/ML and data processing tools while the model is running.

2. Results

The GeoGate is designed to connect ESMF/NUOPC-compliant Earth system model components to harness the data provided by each component (Fig. 1a). The GeoGate co-processing component acts like a regular physical model component, but it is specialized for large-scale data interaction. It can process data flowing from several model components or produce data via interacting with AI/ML-based models to drive other physical model components in a hybrid coupled modeling configuration. In this design, the GeoGate co-processing component mirrors the export state (ESMF's building block to store fields provided by the component) of each connected component (Fig. 1a) as its import state. Then, it creates a separate data channel (Conduit nodes; Harrison et al., 2022) for each individual connection (e.g., ATM, OCN, ICE, and WAV, as shown in Fig. 1b). Then, GeoGate passes data to the desired predefined plugin (I/O, Python, or ParaView Catalyst) to interact with the data. To demonstrate its capabilities, the newly developed GeoGate component is integrated with the ESMF/NUOPC-based UFS-WM. The UFS-WM is a fully coupled earth system model for short- and medium-range research and operational forecasts. For demonstration, the multi-component fully coupled UFS-WM configuration (cpld_control_gefs, including FV3, MOM6, CICE, and WW3 model components) is used. This configuration showcases the ParaView Catalyst (v2) plugin and

Development of High-Resolution Regional Projections of Indian Ocean Chlorophyll-a

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Section 1 - Background

The Indian Ocean has undergone significant changes in recent decades due to human activities and large-scale climate shifts, resulting in altered water chemistry and disturbed marine ecosystems. Climate change processes such as warming, hypoxia, and acidification make the Indian Ocean and its coastal systems highly vulnerable, directly impacting the lives and livelihoods of coastal communities. Recognizing the importance of ocean sciences for sustainable development, the Government of India, through the Ministry of Earth Sciences, has launched the Deep Ocean Mission. A key initiative, the Ocean Climate Change Advisory Services (OCCAS), provides long-term projections of critical climate variables. In this context, we dynamically downscaled Chlorophyll-a to develop model-based insights into future changes in the Indian Ocean.

Section 2 - Regionally Downscaled Model Simulations

A coupled modeling framework integrating the physical Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS) with a lower trophic level biogeochemical model was employed to investigate the future changes in Chlorophyll-a in the subtropical Indian Ocean (30°S–30°N, 30°E–120°E). For regional downscaling, three Earth System Models (ESMs) were selected from the CMIP6 ensemble of 11, based on the availability of essential atmospheric forcing fields and oceanic state variables (physical and biogeochemical) under the SSP5-8.5 scenario (Ghoshal et al., 2025). The chosen ESMs are GFDL-EMS4 (GFDL), UKESM1-0-LL (UKESM), and CNRM-ESM2-1 (CNRM). To reduce biases in the ESM outputs, we applied the Time-Varying Delta (TVD) bias-correction method with respect to ERA5 atmospheric forcings, followed by bias correction of physical and biogeochemical variables using data products described in Chakraborty et al. (2024).

Figure 1: Upper panels (a) & (b) show the model's performance in simulating the annual mean spatial distribution of surface Chlorophyll-a during the historical period. The lower panel (c) shows the model biases (Model – Observation) for surface chlorophyll-a.

Model performance was evaluated by assessing its ability to reproduce historical surface Chlorophyll-a (Figure 1). To assess this, the model-simulated surface Chlorophyll-a is compared with satellite-derived Chlorophyll-a (OC-CCI data product). The spatial distribution of annual mean biases indicates generally weak biases (-0.3 to 0.3 mg/m^3) across the Indian Ocean, except along the western Arabian Sea coast. Positive biases (>0.5 mg/m^3) in the western Arabian Sea, the northeastern Sri Lankan Dome, and near the coasts of Java and Sumatra are attributed to strong vertical mixing simulated by the K-profile parameterization (KPP) scheme, which tends to overestimate upwelling in the regional model.

Section 3 - Near-Future Changes in Surface Chlorophyll-a

Figure 2: The figure presents the spatial mean changes in surface Chlorophyll-a during the near-future period (2015–2040, denoted as Future in the figures). Panels (a), (b), and (c) show outputs from the ROMS_GFDL, ROMS_UKESM, and ROMS_CNRM models, respectively, while panel (d) displays the ensemble mean of these three models.

The mean changes in surface Chlorophyll-a during the near-future period (2015–2040), relative to the historical baseline, are shown in Figure 2. A decrease in surface Chlorophyll-a concentration is evident across most parts of the Indian Ocean. The largest declines (> -0.4 mg/m^3) occur along the western Arabian Sea coast, the southeastern Arabian Sea, and the northeastern Sri Lankan Dome. In contrast, the southern Indian Ocean shows relatively smaller changes in surface Chlorophyll-a compared to the northern Indian Ocean (north of the equator).

This analysis indicates that, during the near-future period, the Arabian Sea, particularly the western Arabian Sea, exhibits the greatest sensitivity of surface Chlorophyll-a to climate change, whereas the southern Indian Ocean (south of 18°S) shows comparatively minimal response.

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A Comparative Analysis of Bias-correction Methods for CMIP6 Atmospheric State Variables Over the Indian Ocean

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Section 1 - Background

The Indian National Center for Ocean Information Services (INCOIS) is developing Ocean Climate Change Advisory Services under the Deep Ocean Mission of the Ministry of Earth Sciences (MoES), India. As part of this initiative, we aim to develop dynamically downscaled, high-resolution coupled (physical and biogeochemical) model simulations.

For future projections, the model requires atmospheric state variables, which are obtained from CMIP6 models. However, these variables often contain systematic biases that need to be addressed to improve their regional representation over the Indian Ocean (IO) (Sabin et al., 2013). The scientific literature offers several statistical bias-correction methods that can be applied to adjust CMIP6-based atmospheric variables (Ghoshal et al., 2025).

Therefore, we seek to identify the most suitable statistical bias-correction method for reducing biases in atmospheric state variables from CMIP6 Earth System Models (ESMs) over the IO domain.

Section 2 - Bias-Correction Methods for CMIP6 Atmospheric Variables

As shown by Ghoshal et al. (2025), Quantile Mapping (QM) and Time-Varying Delta (TVD) are among the best-performing bias-correction methods. Building on this, Ghoshal et al. (2025) proposed a new method, the Ensembled Time-Varying Delta and Quantile Mapping (ETQM), which they demonstrated to be most effective in correcting biases in CMIP6 models for the atmospheric variables air temperature and precipitation rate.

To assess the performance of ETQM in correcting biases in other atmospheric state variables during the historical period (1970-2014) and the future period (2015-2020), we apply ETQM to six additional variables: wind velocities, shortwave and longwave radiation, air pressure, and humidity, which are essential atmospheric forcing fields for ocean models. ERA5 atmospheric data are used as the reference.

In addition to ETQM, we also apply QM and TVD separately to enable a comparative evaluation of their performance. Taylor's Skill Score (TSS) is used to rank the effectiveness of ETQM, QM, and TVD in correcting biases in CMIP6 models. While these methods were applied to six atmospheric variables across three CMIP6 models (GFDL, CNRM, and UKESM), space limitations restrict us to presenting results only for shortwave radiation (RSDS) from the GFDL model. Performance is assessed over the Indian Ocean (IO: 30°S-30°N, 30°E-120°E) and its sub-regions: the Arabian Sea (AS: 0-30°N, 30-78°E), the Bay of Bengal (BoB: 0-30°N, 78-120°E), the Central Indian Ocean (CIO: 0-18°S, 30-120°E), and the Southern Indian Ocean (SIO: 30-18°S, 30-120°E).

Section 3 - Comparative Assessment of Bias-Correction Methods in CMIP6 Models

The TSS analysis for RSDS (Figure 1a) indicates consistent improvements across all IO sub-regions after applying the bias-correction methods. For the entire IO, TSS increases with all approaches, with TVD and ETQM showing slightly better performance than QM. In the AS, all methods enhance skill, with ETQM providing the greatest improvement. In the BoB, where initial model skill is relatively low, performance improves substantially with TVD and ETQM. In the CIO, all methods yield noticeable improvements, with TVD and ETQM performing comparably and better than QM. The SIO already shows high model skill, and only minor improvements are achieved, equally across all three methods. Overall, ETQM delivers the best performance across the IO basin (Figure 1a).

Figure 1: Taylor's Skill Score (a) during the historical period (1970-2014), and (b) in future period (2015-2020) after the bias-correction of RSDS from the GFDL model. RSDS from the ERA5 is used as a reference for bias correction.

For the 2015–2020 period, ETQM records the highest TSS in the AS, followed by TVD (Figure 1b). In the BoB and CIO, all methods improve TSS relative to the original GFDL RSDS, with ETQM and TVD showing comparable performance. As shown in Figure 1b, the GFDL RSDS already attains a high TSS (0.96) in the SIO, leaving little scope for further improvement after bias correction. Across the entire IO, ETQM again outperforms QM and TVD (Figure 1b).

These results indicate that ETQM is a preferable bias-correction method for reducing biases in atmospheric state variables from CMIP6 models. Its key advantage lies in avoiding trend overcorrection (particularly for 2071–2100) by constraining CMIP6-simulated variables to the probability distribution of reference data, while also avoiding the simple preservation of original CMIP6 trends. Instead, ETQM achieves a balance between these two approaches, producing more reliable bias-corrected atmospheric state variables.

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Upgrade of the JMA Sub-Seasonal and Seasonal Ensemble Prediction System (JMA/MRI-CPS4)

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1. Introduction

The next-generation sub-seasonal and seasonal ensemble prediction system (JMA/MRI-CPS4, or simply CPS4) developed by the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) enhances the accuracy of One-month Forecasts, Three-month Forecasts and Warm/cold-season Forecasts, and is scheduled to replace CPS3 (Hirahara et al. 2023) around January 2026. Like CPS3, the CPS4 forecast model is a coupled atmosphere-land-ocean-sea ice type. This report outlines enhancements over CPS3 and the results of re-forecast verification.

2. System Overview

The atmosphere-land surface model used in CPS4 is largely based on that of CPS3, which is an enhanced version of JMA-GSM2003 (Yonehara et al. 2020) for seasonal prediction. CPS4 features refined cloud, stratocumulus and cumulus convection schemes, land-snow and lake models, and other elements.

- The probability density function (PDF) used in the partial cloud scheme based on Smith (1990) has been modified to allow distribution skewed toward the moist regime.
- The PDF width is adjusted to mitigate excessive low clouds over mid-latitude ocean areas.
- The conditions for stratocumulus scheme (Kawai et al. 2017) triggering have been revised to mitigate shortwave radiation flux biases resulting in a warm SST bias off the coast of Peru.
- Excessive orographic rainfall has been mitigated by adjusting the effects of bottom-level updraft forcing in the cumulus convection scheme.
- The deep convection scheme is more active than in CPS3 when the environment is dry.
- The land-snow model incorporates revised snow albedo parameters, formulation of snow cover fractions, and a new snow unloading scheme to enhance land surface albedo. The rain-snow partitioning scheme, the snow compaction scheme and snow thermal conductivity have also been revised to enhance snow depth and density data.
- The CPS lake model (Adachi et al. 2025) has been modified with variable water temperature at the bottom layer to enhance winter lake ice concentration data.
- Prognostic ozone with linear ozone photochemistry parametrization is used in the radiation process instead of the monthly climatology derived from MRI-CCM2 reanalysis (Deushi and Shibata 2011) used in CPS3, resulting in enhanced representation of stratospheric circulation.
- The number of vertical layers has been increased from 100 to 128.
- Initial perturbation has been changed from the Breeding of Growth Modes (BGMs) to a combination of the Singular Vectors (SVs) and Local Ensemble Transform Kalman Filter (LETKF) methods.
- The Stochastic Humidity Profile for Convective Parametrization (SHPC) scheme has been introduced for perturbed members to represent uncertainties in cumulus convection parametrization (Ota 2025).

The ocean and sea ice models have been upgraded to Meteorological Research Institute Community Ocean Model Version 5.0 (MRI.COMv5.0; Sakamoto et al. 2023), whose Leapfrog Adams Moulton (LFAM3) time integration method allows a longer baroclinic time step and reduces computational costs.

CPS4 takes over the role of backing the issuance of One-month Forecasts from the Global Ensemble Prediction System (GEPS). Operational prediction will run every day with five members as per CPS3, but on Tuesdays and Wednesdays the ensemble is enhanced to 25 members up to the one-month lead. Similarly, five-member re-forecasts are enhanced to 13 members up to the one-month lead.

3. Verification Based on Re-forecast Experimentation (1991 – 2020)

Figure 1 shows SST biases. CPS4 reduces cold biases in the eastern Indian Ocean (IO) and mid-latitudes for boreal summer and in the eastern Equatorial Pacific due to enhancement of the cloud and cumulus convection scheme. Figure 2 shows a composite of outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) flux starting from an initial date when the convectively active phase of the Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO) is present in the IO. In relation to GEPS, CPS4 reproduces the slow eastward progression of the MJO as well as CPS3.

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Figure 1: SST biases of (a, d) CPS4, (b, e) CPS3, and (c, f) related differences. (a – c) JJA and (d – f) DJF with 1-month prediction lead.

Figure 2: Longitude-time composite for OLR anomalies averaged at 5°S – 5°N for predictions starting with the MJO’s convectively active phase in the IO, based on 5 members for each initial date in 305 cases.

The convection permitting configuration of the Regional Earth System Model RegCM-ES: simulation of the seasonal precipitation over the Northern Adriatic Region

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Introduction

The Northern Adriatic region is characterized by a complex topography with a presence of several chain mountains (rectangular box in ATM in Figure 1, left panel), a relatively flat valley with a complex river network (River in Figure 1, left panel), significant air-sea interactions which drives deep water formations processes in the Northern Adriatic Sea (OCE in Figure 1, left panel) as well as severe thunderstorms over the land. Here we describe the convection permitting configuration of the Regional Earth System Model RegCM-ES (Sitz et al., 2017; Reale et al., 2020) and show its added value in simulating the seasonal precipitation over the region.

The Regional Earth System Model RegCM-ES

The RegCM-ES (Figure 1, right panel) is composed by the Regional Climate Model v5 (RegCM5/CLM5/CLMU, Giorgi et al., 2023) with a horizontal resolution of 3 km and 41 vertical levels (convection permitting, ATM), the ocean module MITgcm (OCE, Marshall et al., 1997a,b) with an horizontal resolution of approximately 700 m and 59 vertical levels (non-hydrostatic), and (iii) a river discharge module CHyM (RIVER, Coppola et al, 2007) with an horizontal resolution of approximately 1 km. The run of each component of the system and the exchanges of the fields is managed by a driver based on the Earth System Modeling Framework (ESMF). The model uses as initial and boundary conditions the ECWMF ERA5 reanalysis for ATM (Hersbach et al., 2020) and Copernicus Marine Service Physical Reanalysis for OCE (Escudier et al., 2021). The model has been run in evaluation mode starting from August, 1st 1987 onwards.

Figure 1

Results

Figure 2 shows the simulated total precipitation (in mm) in winter (DJF, a), spring (MAM, c), summer (JJA, e) and autumn (SON, g) in the EURO4AM dataset (Isotta et al., 2014). Panel b, d, f, h shows the minimum biases (contour lines) between the simulated values and the observations, while in shaded colors the added

values (AV) defined as $100 * \frac{\text{abs}(\text{BiasRegCM5}) - \text{abs}(\text{BiasRegCM-ES})}{\text{abs}(\text{BiasRegCM5})}$. When $AV > 0$ the coupled model improves the simulation of the precipitation. It is clear that the coupled system improves the simulation of the precipitation over the domain mainly in SON (that is the wettest season over the domain) in the Po Valley and at lee of chain mountains (Figure 2h). This improvement is likely linked to a better representation in the coupled system of the air-sea interaction and transport of moisture from the sea to the inland.

Figure 2

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2

Global and regional climate models: response to forcing, impact studies, subseasonal and seasonal forecasting

Assessing the Indian Ocean Dipole Predictability in MMCFSv1: Role of Subsurface Ocean Dynamics

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Introduction

Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) plays an important role in the tropical Indian Ocean climate variability, characterized by a zonal gradient of sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies between the western (WEIO) and eastern equatorial Indian Ocean (EEIO). The positive IOD event is marked by anomalously warm WEIO and cooler EEIO which results in above-normal rainfall to East Africa and droughts over Indonesia and Australia, while strongly modulating the Indian summer monsoon. Conversely, a negative IOD event with cooler WEIO and warmer EEIO exerts opposite impacts by flipping the rainfall and drought patterns. With the strong influence of IOD on rainfall, agriculture, and socio-economic activities across the Indo-Pacific rim, accurate prediction of IOD events is a key requirement for regional climate services.

Predicting IOD remains a challenge due to its strong coupling with both ocean and atmosphere processes. The seasonal cycle of the thermocline - the boundary between warmer surface water and cooler deep water, along with the role of deeper ocean currents, and the feedback processes collectively play a role in IOD evolution. Model IOD forecast often encounters biases, especially in simulating thermocline depth, SST gradients and rainfall teleconnections, limiting the skill of IOD forecasts. Previous studies highlighted that coupled forecast systems tend to show excessive amplitude in simulated IOD events, exhibiting a weaker link between surface and subsurface ocean processes. Studies have shown errors in the representation of climate pattern like El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO)-IOD interactions, thereby reducing reliability at longer lead times. The Monsoon Mission Coupled Forecast System version 1 (MMCFSv1) has been widely used for seasonal prediction of monsoon variability. While MMCFSv1 has demonstrated skill in simulating large-scale climate modes such as ENSO, its performance in forecasting IOD events has not been extensively evaluated.

This study evaluates the seasonal predictive capability of MMCFSv1 for IOD during the period 1982–2016. Study uses diagnostics methods that combine surface SST anomalies, subsurface ocean thermocline depth, and coupled feedback mechanisms. Analysis examines the model's skill in reproducing the Dipole Mode Index (DMI), the leading modes of SST variability, the role of subsurface anomalies, and the correlations between observed and simulated fields. With the comparative analysis of model and observed data the study aims to identify key strengths and limitations of the model in representing IOD dynamics also the IOD evolution, with strong seasonal dependence between (June-August) JJA onset and (September-November) SON for improving seasonal forecasts.

Model and Data

MMCFSv1 is a fully coupled ocean-atmosphere general circulation model developed for extended range and seasonal prediction under the Indian Monsoon Mission initiative. The atmospheric component is based on NCEP CFSv2, with a horizontal resolution of T382 (38 km). The ocean component is based on the MOM4p0d ocean model, with a horizontal resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ near the equator. For this study, we use May Initial Conditions (ICs) to generate seasonal forecasts for June–August (JJA) and September–November (SON) seasons for the period 1982–2016. These lead times capture the evolution of IOD events during their developing (JJA) and mature (SON) phases.

Study uses observations and reanalysis datasets essential for evaluating the simulations from the MMCFSv1. The ERA5 reanalysis daily sea surface temperature (SST), SST anomalies, and U and V wind components at a 0.25° resolution, covering the period from 1982 to 2016 are used. For the observed thermocline depth, the data comes from the Global Ocean Data Assimilation System (GODAS) monthly temperature profiles, where thermocline depth is defined as the depth of the 20°C isotherm. In the model, thermocline depth is extracted from MMCFSv1 subsurface temperature fields by identifying the depth where the temperature crosses 20°C . This interpolation is carried out for every grid point and time step, both in the model and the observed temperature profiles.

Results

In Figure 1, the result highlights the ability of MMCFSv1 May IC to capture the interannual variability of the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD). The JJAS DMI detrended time series (Fig.1a) shows that the model successfully reproduces most positive and negative IOD events during 1982-2016, compared to observations. Although MMCFSv1 slightly

Figure 1: IOD Diagnostics from MMCFSv1 May IC and Observations for 1982–2016: (a) Detrended JJAS: DMI Time Series, (b) EOF Modes of JJAS: SST Anomalies, and (c) SST–Wind Correlation Patterns during Positive IOD Events.

underestimates the amplitude of extreme events, the overall correlation between the modeled and observed DMI remains significant, indicating a skilled seasonal forecasting ability from the initial May condition.

The spatial patterns of SST variability derived from the EOF analysis (Fig. 1b) further demonstrate the model’s ability to reproduce the canonical IOD mode. The first EOF mode in MMCFSv1 shows a dipole structure with warm anomalies over the western equatorial Indian Ocean (WEIO) and cool anomalies over the eastern equatorial Indian Ocean (EEIO), closely resembling the observed mode. The SST-wind correlations (Fig. 1c) also show consistency with the physical processes of the development of the IOD, with enhanced easterly wind anomalies over the central equatorial Indian Ocean coinciding with the cooling of SST in the EEIO, suggesting that the model captures the coupled air–sea feedbacks.

The results in Figure 2 focus on the relationship between SST and thermocline depth (D_{20}), a key driver of IOD evolution. Panel (a) shows that the correlation between observed SST and observed D_{20} is high in the EEIO during JJA and SON, confirming that shallow thermocline conditions favour cold SST anomalies during positive IOD events. MMCFSv1 replicates this relationship, though with slightly weaker correlations. Panel. It signifies the shallow thermocline conditions are closely linked to cooler SSTs, a key mechanism driving positive IOD events due to negative correlations EEIO. The MMCFSv1 model captures this relationship reasonably well, suggesting that while the model reproduces the essential thermocline–SST feedback, it may underestimate its intensity. Panel (b) further illustrates a clear linear relationship between detrended SST anomalies and D_{20} anomalies, with higher IOD index values corresponding to stronger negative D_{20} anomalies in the EEIO. This highlights the importance of accurately simulating thermocline depth variability to improve IOD prediction skill. Further analysis using MMCFSv2 is planned to evaluate whether advancements in model physics and resolution can reduce coupled biases, improve thermocline representation, and enhance the seasonal predictability of the IOD.

Figure 2: Relationship Between SST and D_{20} for IOD Diagnostics: (a) Correlation of Observed SST with Observed and Model D_{20} during JJA and SON (1982–2016), and (b) Scatter plots of SST and D_{20} Anomalies with IOD Index for JJA and SON (Detrended).

Climate-Driven Variability of Groundwater Recharge in Arid and Semi-Arid Africa: A Regional Modeling Perspective

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Introduction

In Africa, Groundwater is an essential water source for domestic, agricultural, and industrial activities in arid and semi-arid regions. However, groundwater recharge in these regions is extremely sensitive to climate variability and change. Limited precipitation, high evapotranspiration, and infrequent rainfall lead to complex and variable recharge systems. Predicting groundwater recharge in their changing climate conditions is critical for planning and managing water resources. Advances in coupled Regional Climate Models (RCMs) and hydrological models permits an assessment and projection of regional groundwater recharge variability. Nonetheless, challenges remain in climate projection downscaling, estimating recharge in data-sparse regions, and representation of land-atmosphere interactions.

Methodological Overview

Recharge variability in arid and semi-arid Africa is assessed using RCMs (e.g. CORDEX Africa) or GCMs, downscaled for use in hydrological models such as SWAT and WaterGAP, and bias-corrected to remove model errors (Ali et al., 2022). The coupled models analyze spatiotemporal recharge variability as a function of soils, land use and water input data, and validated using mediocre satellite data (e.g. GRACE, SMAP) or comparable data in some cases.

Climate Forcing and Response

Forecasted changes in the intensity, duration, and interval of rainfall have a direct effect on recharge events. In this regard, increased temperatures raise evapotranspiration, and subsequent net recharge, even with infrequent extraordinary rainfall events, drops. Research shows that recharge across semi-arid Africa is closely linked to variations in seasonal precipitation associated with larger climate systems such as the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and Indian Ocean Dipole (Taylor et al., 2018). Recharge tends to occur in short bursts after intense storms, which supports investigating sub-seasonal and seasonal climate forecasts to see how the principal rainfall and recharge systems follow a similar behavior and pattern. The uncertainty in an RCM's projected thunderstorms and convective rain performance detracts from overall confidence in future recharge estimates.

Impact Studies

Recharge instability endangers sustainable water supplies and jeopardizes ecosystems and livelihoods, especially those of farmers using shallow aquifers. Reductions in water table levels have reversed good actions taken to protect wetlands and oases. Unplanned recharge can cause unintended consequences and unravel during droughts and water scarcity crises. Scientists call for immediate action regarding groundwater management, advocating for the adoption of managed aquifer recharge (MAR) and climate adaptive policies (Zhang et al., 2021).

Sub-seasonal and Seasonal Forecasting

Regional climate models can reasonably identify season aperture precipitation forecast values, but repeatedly struggle to provide an accurate forecast of groundwater recharge, involving precipitation bias, precipitation timing, weak soil moisture feedback, and problematic incorporation of groundwater modelling physically. Throughout Africa, standalone, real-time time series hydroclimatic data (e.g. soil moisture, vegetation indices, evapotranspiration) was successfully employed in regional recharge forecasting in select short-term forecasts. Where to from here leads to forecasting, modelling and utilization of seasonal climate predictions combined with land surface models to further improve yet to be imminent drought early warning systems.

Conclusion

Significant obstacles to sustainable water resource management in entire Africa's arid and semi-arid regions due to uncertainty regarding climate-induced groundwater recharge are ongoing. Though recent progress using regional climate models has revealed some factors influencing recharge dynamics, challenges remain for sub-seasonal and seasonal variability. Remediation of these knowledge gaps will involve a more composite approach that extends observational networks, downscaling approaches, and the integration of socio-hydrological processes. Researchers must also invest in hybrid modelling frameworks that combine process-based understanding with data-driven analysis to improve actionable groundwater recharge forecasts, a necessary action to improve water security for the most vulnerable populations in Africa.

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Streamflow Simulation using WRF-Hydro Model over the Cauvery River Basin

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Background

Understanding the hydrological cycle is crucial for managing water resources and assessing risks associated with water, such as drought and floods. (Liu et al., 2008). In this study the large-scale hydrologic modeling system WRF-Hydro is used to assess the streamflow simulation. This modeling framework was developed by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) to simulate the movement of water through the land surface and river channels (Gochis et al., 2018). WRF-Hydro is the hydrologic extension of Weather Research Forecasting (WRF) model, which is a next generation numerical weather prediction system. The model can be run in two modes standalone and coupled with the WRF atmospheric model to understand feedback between land and atmosphere. It incorporates key hydrological processes such as surface and subsurface runoff, channel routing, and land-atmosphere interactions, making it suitable for large-scale hydrologic application (i.e., streamflow forecasting, flood modeling, and water resources analysis). To estimate land surface fluxes such as sensible, latent heat, and net radiation in the 1-dimensional column land surface model, WRF-Hydro provides various physics options. The land surface model also estimates soil moisture dynamics in four different layers, canopy interception, canopy transpiration and rainfall partitioning at land into surface runoff and infiltration. In the present study, standalone WRF-Hydro model is set-up with one domain over the entire Cauvery basin boundary (Figure 1a). The parent domain covers the Southern part of India with a spatial resolution of 5 km.

Figure 1(a) Study area showing reservoir stations marked as black dots from upstream to downstream (1=Kudige, 2=Kollegal, 3=Bilungundulu, 4=Urachikottai, 5=Kodumudi, 6=Musuri) located in sub-basins. **(b)** Timeseries of daily streamflow estimates (m³/s) over six stations in the Cauvery River basin for 2003.

Model Setup and Preprocessing

In this study, GLDAS version 2.1 data sets are used as forcing data during the period of 2001-2022 in the WRF-Hydro model, which is available with a spatial resolution of 0.25 and a temporal resolution of 3 hours. GLDAS data provided by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Goddard Space Flight

Center (GSFC) Hydrological Sciences Laboratory (HSL) are the combination of satellite and ground-based observational data products (Rodell et al., 2004). Meteorological forcings for the model run, 3-hourly dataset are prepared air temperature, shortwave and longwave radiation, surface pressure, specific humidity, near-surface U and V wind speed components and precipitation. To create hydrological grids for the NOAH-MP module, we use digital elevation model (DEM) raster and forecast points. In addition to meteorological forcing datasets, the model also utilizes soil properties and general information is available at the NCAR. The spatial soil variability data are prepared using R utility script provided by the NCAR. Furthermore, streamflow in situ data is obtained for 6 stations in the Cauvery River Basin from the Central Water Commission (CWC), India. Daily rainfall observations at 0.25° spatial resolution are acquired from India Meteorology Department (IMD). For setting up the hydrologic model domain, high-resolution terrain data such as flow direction, flow accumulation, and stream networks derived from Digital Elevation Model (DEM), land use land cover, soil type, and watershed boundaries and streamorder, are processed and resampled to match the routing grid. To create the watershed delineation boundaries, the latitude and longitude of each station located within the basin boundary are used. Further, the delineation tool identifies the upstream area that contributes runoff to the discharge location, thereby defining the watershed boundary. This confirms that the modeled watershed aligns with the observed location for accurate streamflow comparison and calibration.

Results

Figure 1b shows the streamflow comparison between WRF-Hydro-simulated streamflow (blue line) and observed streamflow (green line) across six stations for the year 2003. Results show that across all stations, especially at the downstream sites, the model consistently overestimates streamflow, with peak flows and baseflows both appearing higher than observed values. Lower Cauvery Basin covers more than 50% of total area of the basin of the total area of the basin, which lies mainly in the Tamil Nadu state and receives rainfall mainly from the Northeast Monsoon (October to December). In contrast, upper Cauvery basin located in Karnataka, is primarily dependent on the Southwest Monsoon during June to September. The spatial variation in rainfall patterns impacts the hydrological response of the basin. The time series of streamflow observation during October to December illustrates that streamflow is comparatively higher at the station present in the lower basin due to the rainfall contribution from the Northeast Monsoon. The overestimation in model simulation suggests insufficient infiltration or storage in the model, or uncalibrated routing parameters that lead to excessive runoff. The model will be calibrated to improve the accuracy of the streamflow predictions and will be ultimately utilized to subseasonal to seasonal (S2S) streamflow prediction using forcings derived from operational S2S forecasts.

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Assessing Precipitation Climatology Using a High-Resolution Coupled Regional Ocean–Atmosphere Model (RSM-ROMS)

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Abstract

Utilizing the coupled RSM-ROMS model, which is driven by NCEP-R2 reanalysis data, we assess the precipitation climatology across Kenya, Central America, and Northern Australia. Our findings indicate that the regional climate model effectively captures the spatial patterns of precipitation; however, it does exhibit a notable wet bias. These results underscore the efficacy of dynamical downscaling. Future research will expand this methodology to include CMIP6-driven simulations, enabling more accurate regional projections.

1. Introduction

Regional climate modelling plays a crucial role in overcoming the limitations of coarse-resolution global climate models (GCMs), which often fail to capture fine-scale regional processes due to their horizontal resolution of several hundred kilometers. Studies have shown that increasing model resolution significantly improves the simulation of precipitation, surface fluxes, cloudiness, and circulation features (e.g., Hertwig et al. 2015). High-resolution simulations, though computationally challenging, provide more realistic representations of regional climate variability and extremes. To bridge the gap between global-scale forcing and regional-scale processes, dynamical downscaling with nested Regional Climate Models (RCMs) offers a widely used approach, where GCM outputs are used to drive RCMs over specific regions, yielding detailed and reliable information for climate impact assessments. The RCMs serve a critical role in understanding the regional climate in ways that statistical downscaling including AI/ML, although computationally effective, are limited in their ability to shed light on physical and or mechanistic understanding of the variations.

At Florida State University, we employ a Coupled Regional Ocean–Atmosphere Model, in which the Regional Spectral Model (RSM; Juang and Kanamitsu, 1994) is coupled with the Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS; Shchepetkin and McWilliams, 2005), hereafter referred to as RSM-ROMS. This coupled RCM effectively resolves key mesoscale features and captures crucial ocean–atmosphere interactions, making it a useful tool for regional climate studies across different parts of the world. Uniquely, we find coupled ocean-atmosphere rectification in high resolution RSM-ROMS forced by coarse global reanalysis/General Circulation Models (GCMs), especially in the coastal regions (Misra and Mishra 2016). Here, we present results from RSM-ROMS simulations forced with the coarse-resolution NCEP-R2 reanalysis, with a particular focus on its ability to reproduce verifiable precipitation patterns, thereby highlighting the value of regional coupled modelling as a tool to advance our understanding of regional climate processes.

2. Coupled Modeling Framework

The RSM-ROMS is a primitive equation model using spectral discretization for the dynamical core and a suite of physics schemes suited for simulating regional climate (e.g., Misra et al., 2018). Key parameterizations include the Relaxed Arakawa–Schubert scheme for deep convection (Moorthi & Suarez, 1992), the Tiedtke (1983) scheme for shallow convection, the Hong and Pan (1996) planetary boundary layer scheme, the Noah land surface model, and cloud–radiation schemes following Zhao & Carr (1997). Its oceanic component, ROMS is a free-surface, terrain-following ocean model configured with 30 vertical levels and a nonlocal K-profile closure scheme for vertical mixing (Large et al., 1994).

The RSM and ROMS are directly coupled on the same 20-km grid using an efficient parallel coupling strategy, with fluxes exchanged every hour without the need for interpolation or flux adjustment. The atmospheric lateral boundary conditions are taken from the NCEP–DOE Reanalysis (R2) at 6-hourly intervals, while the oceanic boundary conditions are provided by the Simple Ocean Data Assimilation

(SODA) v2.2.4 at monthly intervals. All inputs are consistently interpolated to the RSM–ROMS grid, ensuring seamless coupling and a realistic representation of mesoscale ocean–atmosphere interactions.

3. Results & Discussion

Precipitation is a key variable with direct societal impacts and serves as a primary indicator of a model’s ability to capture essential climate processes. Here, we present RSM-ROMS simulated precipitation climatology for three regions where the RCM has been configured: Kenya (Figure 1a, b; Misra and Jayasankar, 2025), Central America (Figure 1c, d; Misra and Jayasankar, 2024a), and Northern Australia (Figure 1e, f; Misra and Jayasankar, 2024b). Figure 1 shows the climatology of mean seasonal rainfall over three regions during their respective rainy seasons — June to September for Kenya, and Central America, and October to March for Northern Australia. In comparison to IMERG observations, RSM-ROMS captures the spatial heterogeneity of precipitation climatology, though it exhibits a wet bias across all three regions. This regional model requires further tuning to reduce these uncertainties; however, when examining other variables, we often find that RSM-ROMS outperforms the global reanalysis/GCMs used to force the simulations (not shown), highlighting the potential value of dynamical downscaling. In the future, we aim to use the RCM driven by CMIP6 models to investigate future projections at regional scale.

Figure 1: Seasonal climatology of precipitation (1985–2014) from (a, c, e) observations, (b) and (b, d, f) RSM–ROMS for the region a, b) Kenya, c, d) Central America and e, f) Northern Australia.

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Advances in forecast/ NWP models: case studies, predictability, ensembles

Evaluation of Wrf Model Performance in Simulating Track and Rainfall of Super Cyclones Gonu (2007) and Amphan (2020)

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1. Introduction:

Tropical cyclones are a significant threat to coastal communities, leading to widespread damage and loss of life from high winds, storm surges, and torrential rainfall. The ability to accurately predict the path and precipitation of these events is crucial for effective early warning systems and disaster management. Numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, such as the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model, are fundamental tools used for this purpose. This study evaluates the performance of the WRF model (v4.5) in simulating two high-impact super cyclones: Gonu (2007), the strongest recorded cyclone in the Arabian Sea, and Amphan (2020), one of the costliest in the Bay of Bengal. By analyzing these two contrasting events, this research aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of the WRF model's capabilities and limitations in diverse geographical and meteorological conditions. The findings will contribute to the ongoing effort to improve the accuracy of operational cyclone forecasting in the North Indian Ocean basin.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 Rainfall Simulation

A primary objective of this study was to evaluate the WRF model's ability to simulate the spatial distribution of rainfall, which is critical for flood-related disaster management. The model output was compared against satellite-based GPM (Global Precipitation Measurement) observations. As illustrated in Fig.1, a series of daily plots for Super Cyclone Gonu demonstrates the model's performance in this regard.

Figure 1: WRF Simulated Daily Rainfall with Cyclone Gonu Tracks (IMD vs WRF)

The WRF simulated track (blue dashed line) closely follows the observed IMD track (red line with markers) for each day of the cyclone's life cycle. Crucially, the model successfully simulated the overall spatial pattern of heavy rainfall (indicated by the darker shading) associated with the cyclone's movement. From June 1st to June 6th, the model correctly placed the bands of intense precipitation around the eye of the storm. As the cyclone approached the coastline of Oman, the model accurately captured the widespread heavy rainfall over land, which is vital for issuing flood warnings. While quantitative analysis revealed that the model

had a tendency to slightly overestimate peak rainfall intensity in some areas, the overall accuracy in spatial distribution is a significant strength of the WRF simulation.

2.2 Track Simulation Accuracy

The WRF model's performance in simulating the cyclone tracks was quantitatively evaluated by comparing the model output with official IMD best-track data. As shown in Fig. 2, the track error for both Super Cyclone Gonu and Amphan was plotted as a function of time from the start of the simulation.

Figure 2: WRF vs IMD Comparison of Track Accuracy for Super Cyclones Amphan (2020) and Gonu (2007)

The results indicate that the WRF model's performance in track prediction was consistent for both cyclones. For Cyclone Gonu (green line), the track error generally increased over the first 72 hours before decreasing as the cyclone made landfall. The final error was a manageable 84.6 km at 144 hours. For Cyclone Amphan (blue line), the track error showed a steady increase, reaching a maximum of 144.7 km at 120 hours. Despite these deviations, the overall mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE) for both cyclones were remarkably similar, with MAE of 107.4 km for Amphan and 107.1 km for Gonu. This similarity across different basins demonstrates the model's reliability in forecasting the path of cyclones in the North Indian Ocean.

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Operational KIM4.0 Upgrade for Global Medium-Range Prediction

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1. Introduction

The Korean Integrated Model (KIM) was developed by the Korea Institute of Atmospheric Prediction Systems (KIAPS) during the first KIAPS project (2011–2019). The Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA) began operating KIM in April 2020 with version 3.5, featuring a horizontal resolution of 12 km. Recently, the 8 km resolution version, KIM4.0, was completed, and operational runs commenced in May 2025. Along with the resolution increase, the scale-aware parameterization in the convection scheme has been revised to support the transition from 12 km to 8 km resolution, leading to improved forecast skill. This upgrade also includes an increase in data assimilation resolution from 32 km to 24 km.

2. Key features of the KIM4.0 Upgrade

Table 1 summarizes the major upgrades in KIM4.0. The primary enhancement involves increased horizontal resolution for both the model (from 12 km to 8 km) and data assimilation (from 32 km to 24 km). Evaluations have demonstrated that these improvements positively impact the reduction of global forecast errors (Lee et al., 2025). However, it has also revealed that physics schemes can be sensitive to model resolution, potentially causing degraded features depending on their scale-awareness design. Recently, Han (2025) revised the scale-aware parameterization of the KSAS convection scheme in KIM to improve both global simulations and local high-impact weather predictions. The KIM4.0 upgrade adopts this revised CPS and includes further optimization of the CPS trigger parameters, which are particularly impactful for capturing heavy rainfall signals around the Korean Peninsula, especially under highly baroclinic conditions. Additional physics developments from the early stage (2020-2022) of the second KIAPS project are incorporated into KIM4.0.

Table 1: Key features of KIM4.0 upgrade

Process	Major Update
Horizontal resolution	Model 12 km → 8 km Data assimilation 32 km → 24km
Surface initialization	Land initialization: CDF revision. Consistency with land model physic Sea-ice temperature initialization modified
Physics	Revised scale-aware parameters in CPS + Modified scale-aware parameters in convective updrafts Updates and corrections in ozone & aerosol climatology Modification in the cloud overlapping method Implementation of topographic effects on shortwave RAD
Framework	New grid partitioning, KIM-IO upgrade Speed optimization for scientific workflow components Code refactoring

3. Evaluation and forecast performance

KIM4.0 demonstrates overall superior performance in global simulations, as summarized in the scorecard in Fig. 1. Specifically, there is an approximately ~3.5% reduction in error for +5-day geopotential height forecasts at 500 hPa over the northern extratropics, based on the monthly average. Slight degradation is observed in the southern hemisphere, likely due to the discarding of some operational physics optimizations, which will be addressed in future upgrades. In terms of precipitation, KIM4.0 shows notable improvements, particularly in simulating strong signals associated with heavy rainfall events. This improvement is partially reflected in the statistical precipitation skill scores shown in Fig. 1b, where the new version outperforms KIM3.9 across all precipitation thresholds. The enhanced simulation performance is especially evident in terrain-following features over the Korean Peninsula, such as snowfall along eastern mountain regions (not shown).

Currently, the KMA plans to upgrade the next version, focusing on enhancements in data assimilation and physics revisions. KIAPS is also developing a next-generation KIM with new configurations, such as ~km scale short-range prediction systems for regional domains and extended-prediction systems with coupled models. These advancements are scheduled for release after the completion of the KIAPS' second project in 2026.

Figure 1: Performance evaluation of KIM4.0 versus KIM3.9. (a) scorecard comparing global RMSE against analysis for January 2023 (00 UTC), with green indicating improvement and red indicating degradation. (b) Frequency bias and equitable threat score of 24-h accumulated precipitation (+3-day prediction) over South Korea and Asia, verified against gauge observations in August 2022.

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Upgrade of JMA's Operational Global Numerical Weather Prediction System

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Introduction

In March 2025, the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) upgraded its operational global numerical weather prediction system by introducing a revised version of its Global Spectral Model (GSM). The revision involved refinements of parallelization and data structure to reduce computational resource usage, and parametrized radiation and land surface processes, thereby improving forecasting over the previous version (Yonehara et al. 2023), particularly for the mid- and high latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere. This report outlines individual components of the upgrade and related verification results.

Main Updates

Parallelization and Data Structure

The two-dimensional decomposition method adopted for parallelization among MPI processes was enhanced. The previous GSM used different domain decompositions for semi-Lagrangian advection scheme calculation and other grid-point based calculations such as physical parametrization (JMA 2025). In the updated model, all grid-point based processes are computed in the same domain with fewer MPI communications. In association, the decomposition approach in the data assimilation system was also enhanced. These updates led to a reduction in computational resources such as memory usage. Additionally, the structure for grid-point model data in the GSM was upgraded, enabling more flexible adaptation to computing architecture characteristics.

Radiation

The globally uniform climatological annual mean used for carbon dioxide concentration was updated from 396.0 ppmv (the 2013 observation value) to 417.9 ppmv (the 2022 value)(WMO 2023). This reduced temperature biases in the stratosphere through strengthened cooling due to increased longwave radiation emissions. Radiation scheme calculations were also optimized.

Land Surface

The Leaf Area Index (LAI) monthly climatology was updated to a gridded version, as opposed to the previous average over tropical, temperate and boreal latitudinal zones for each vegetation type. The updated data are derived from a more recent MODIS product (Myneni et al. 2002) featuring higher resolution and greater accuracy than the version used in the previous model (Yan et al. 2016 a, b). The update enables more realistic representation of LAI distribution, leading to a reduction in temperature and relative humidity biases in the lower troposphere through enhanced forecast accuracy for sensible and latent heat fluxes.

Verification results

The effects of parallelization enhancement were evaluated through two experiments run from a single initial condition. Figure 1 shows reduced memory usage for 132-hour forecasts and 4D-Var.

The two performance evaluation experiments (TEST for the updated system and CNTL for the previous one) covered July to September 2023 (summer) and December to February 2023/2024 (winter). Figure 2 shows vertical profiles of mean errors (ME) in temperature for CNTL and TEST averaged over summer. Cold biases in the lower troposphere and warm biases in the stratosphere were reduced, mainly due to the update of LAI monthly climatology and carbon dioxide concentration climatology, respectively.

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Figure 1: Maximum per-node memory usage [MiB] of jobs (132-hour forecasts (FcEf, Tq959) and 4D-Var (Fdv, Tl319)) among all computing nodes. Blue: CNTL; red: TEST.

Figure 2: Vertical profiles of mean errors for temperature [K] against radiosonde observations in the 20 – 90°N region for the summer experiment. Blue: CNTL; red: TEST. Lines represent ME at different forecast lead times for days 1 to 11.

Introduction of Stochastic Humidity Profile for Convective parametrization (SHPC) method in JMA's Global Ensemble Prediction System

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1. Introduction

The Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) introduced a new model ensemble scheme called the Stochastic Humidity Profile for Convective parametrization (SHPC) into its Global Ensemble Prediction System (GEPS) in March 2025. The SHPC perturbs humidity profile input for convective parametrizations to represent uncertainties in convective activity. It mitigates the issue of under-dispersiveness in the tropics and makes it possible to reduce the excessive amplitude of initial perturbations made from the Singular Vector (SV) method in the tropics.

2. Formulation and Settings

Based on Tompkins and Berner (2008), the SHPC perturbs relative humidity profile input for convective parametrization. Perturbations are generated from random patterns with horizontal and temporal correlations based on the combination of spherical harmonic functions such as the Stochastic Perturbation of Physics Tendency (SPPT) scheme. The perturbation amplitude is at its maximum at the lowest model level, and is exponentially reduced with the logarithm of vertical pressure levels. Figure 1 shows an example of random patterns used for the SHPC. In the experiments described below, the maximum wave number, temporal correlation scale and vertical e-folding scale of perturbations are set as 20, 72 hours and 0.8 (in logarithm with pressure levels), respectively. The perturbation standard deviation at the lowest model level is approximately 4%, and perturbations are truncated at +/-10%. Perturbation amplitude is adjusted so as not to induce supersaturation and negative humidity in the input humidity profile.

3. Experiments

To verify system performance for medium-range forecasts with lead times of up to 11 days, retrospective experiments covering periods of one month or more for summer 2021 (12UTC initials from 21 July 2021 to 11 September 2021) and winter 2021/22 (12UTC initials from 21 December 2021 to 11 February 2022) were conducted. The CNTL experiment involved the use of the operational GEPS as of March 2024, with the number of ensemble members reduced to 13. In the TEST experiment, the SHPC was applied to CNTL and the amplitude of initial perturbations made from SV in the tropics was reduced to 60%. Figure 2 shows the spread of zonal wind speed at 250 hPa (U250) normalized using the ensemble mean RMSE in the tropics (20°S – 20°N). The spread was reduced by up to three or four days and increased beyond four days. The initial spread reduction observed was due to the lower initial perturbation amplitude. The SHPC mitigated the under-dispersiveness of medium-range forecasts in the tropics. Figure 3 shows Continuous Ranked Probability Scores (CRPSs) of U250 for the tropics. Probabilistic forecast skill was enhanced with better spread-skill relationships. The effect for the extra-tropics was smaller than that for the tropics (not shown).

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Figure 1: Example of a random pattern used for the SHPC.

Figure 2: Spread of zonal wind speed at 250 hPa (U250) normalized using the ensemble mean RMSE for the tropics ($20^{\circ}\text{S} - 20^{\circ}\text{N}$) for summer 2021 (left) and winter 2021/22 (right). Green and red lines show CNTL and TEST, respectively.

Figure 3: As per Figure 2, but for CRPS against analysis (unit: m/s). Purple lines and yellow triangles show CRPS change ratios $((\text{TEST}-\text{CNTL})/\text{CNTL}; \%$, right axis) and statistically significant enhancement at a 95% confidence level with bootstrap application, respectively.

Upgrade of JMA's Global Ensemble Prediction System

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1. Introduction

The Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) upgraded its Global Ensemble Prediction System (Global EPS) on March 18 2025 to incorporate a new model ensemble scheme, reduced amplitude of initial perturbations in the tropics, recent Global Spectral Model (GSM) developments and revised sea surface temperature (SST) perturbations.

2. Major Updates

(1) New model ensemble scheme

A new model ensemble scheme called the Stochastic Humidity Profile for Convective parametrization (SHPC, Ota (2025)) was introduced to represent uncertainty in convective activity and mitigate under-dispersiveness in the tropics.

(2) Reduced amplitude of initial perturbations in the tropics

The amplitude of initial perturbations made from Singular Vector (SV) data for the tropics was reduced to 60% of the previous level.

(3) Recent GSM developments

The forecast model was upgraded to a low-resolution version of the latest GSM (Kawaguchi et al. 2025). The required computational resources are reduced with enhancements in MPI-based parallelization and data transfer.

(4) Revised SST perturbations

SST perturbations were revised so that the ensemble mean SST coincides with the unperturbed SST for all lead times.

3. Verification

To verify system performance for medium-range forecasts with lead times of up to 11 days, retrospective experiments covering periods of three months or more in summer 2023 and winter 2023/24 were conducted. The results showed enhanced spread-skill relationships and continuous ranked probability scores (CRPSs), especially in the tropics (20°S – 20°N). Figure 1 shows the spread normalized by the ensemble mean RMSE, and CRPSs of 250 hPa zonal wind speed (U250) for the tropics in summer. Brier skill scores for precipitation forecasts in Japan were also enhanced for summer (not shown).

Hindcast experiments were also conducted for the 30-year period from 1991 to 2020 with atmospheric initial conditions from the latest Japanese reanalysis (JRA-3Q; Kosaka et al. 2024). Reduced amplitude of initial perturbations and implementation of the SHPC mitigate excessive and insufficient ensemble spreads, respectively (Figure 2). MJO forecast skill was almost neutral for all lead times (not shown).

Figure 1: Spread normalized by the ensemble mean RMSE (left) and CRPS (right; unit: m/s) of zonal wind speed at 250 hPa (U250) in the tropics (20°S – 20°N) for summer 2023. Green and red lines represent verification results for the previous (CNTL) and new (TEST) Global EPS. The purple line and yellow triangles in the panel on the right represent score change ratios $[(\text{TEST}-\text{CNTL})/\text{CNTL}]$, right axis; unit: %) and statistically significant enhancements at a 95% confidence level with bootstrap application, respectively.

Figure 2: Ensemble spread (left; unit: $\times 10^6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$) and spread normalized by the ensemble mean RMSE (right) of velocity potential at 200 hPa in the tropics (20°S – 20°N) for winter 1991 – 2020. Black and red lines represent verification results for the previous (CNTL) and new (TEST) Global EPS, respectively.

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Operational Use of AMSU-A and ATMS Window Channels in JMA's NWP Systems

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1. Introduction

Radiance data collected by satellite-based microwave sounders mainly provide information on the vertical distribution of atmospheric temperature and humidity, as assimilated in JMA's Global Analysis (GA), Meso-scale Analysis (MA) and Local Analysis (LA) systems. AMSU-A and ATMS microwave sounders are equipped with window channels that have higher transmittance in the atmosphere than sounding channels and are sensitive to humidity at lower-tropospheric levels. These channels are used only for Quality Control (QC), but are considered capable of contributing to more accurate weather forecast by enhancing analysis humidity fields.

2. Methodology

2.1. Channel Selection

In this study, window channels with frequencies of 23.8 GHz (AMSU-A/ch1 and ATMS/ch1) and 31.4 GHz (AMSU-A/ch2, ATMS/ch2) were assimilated. 89 GHz channels (AMSU-A/ch15 and ATMS/ch16) are also sensitive to humidity at lower-tropospheric levels, but were not assimilated because of their higher sensitivity to ice clouds and precipitation, which complicates QC processing.

2.2. QC

A clear-sky method was applied in which only data unaffected by clouds or precipitation are assimilated. The same cloud detection scheme used for channels sensitive to temperature at lower-tropospheric levels (Okamoto et al., 2005) using retrieved cloud liquid water and scattering index values was implemented. Only data from areas over oceans are assimilated in consideration of the greater uncertainty of surface emissivity and temperature in the first guess from areas over land and sea ice. Data from areas near land or sea ice are not used in order to avoid contamination of such surfaces within the ocean-based observation footprint. Data at the edge of scans where the observation footprint is larger are also excluded to avoid contamination.

2.3. Observation Errors

Observation errors are defined for each satellite based on the standard deviation of O-B (Observation minus Background) calculated from 15 days of GA statistics (Table 1). These values are inflated in analysis systems because inter-channel and spatial observation error correlations are not considered in assimilation. Error inflation factors are set to match those for microwave imager channels whose frequencies are close to those of the window channels (3.0 for GA, 4.0 for MA and 6.0 for LA).

3. NWP Effects and Results

Numerical experiments were conducted to evaluate the effects of window channels on the global, meso-scale and local NWP systems. Here, the results of experiments involving the meso-scale NWP system for July 2023 and January 2024 are reported.

Window channel assimilation enhanced consistency between the first guess and humidity-sensitive observations such as AMSR2 and the humidity channels of ATMS and CrIS (Fig. 1), which implies better first-guess accuracy. The false alarm and miss ratios compared to radar/raingauge-analyzed precipitation data were reduced for relatively weak precipitation forecasts up to 5 mm/3 h for the summer period. Several case studies also indicated that additional information on lower-tropospheric

humidity provided by the window channels of AMSU-A and ATMS near precipitation areas contributed to better forecast accuracy (Fig. 2). Similar enhancements were observed in the global and local NWP systems.

Based on these results, assimilation of the window channels of AMSU-A and ATMS was adopted in MA and LA in March 2025, and is scheduled for adoption in GA in autumn 2025.

Table 1: Window channel observation error settings [K]

Satellite/Sensor	ch1	ch2
Metop-C/AMSU-A	2.80	2.40
NOAA-15/AMSU-A	3.00	2.60
NOAA-18/AMSU-A	2.80	2.40
NOAA-19/AMSU-A	2.80	2.40
<hr/>		
Suomi-NPP/ATMS	2.80	2.20
NOAA-20/ATMS	3.00	2.70
NOAA-21/ATMS	3.00	2.70

Fig. 1: Ratio of change [%] in the standard deviation of O-B resulting from window channel assimilation in MA. (a) Microwave imagers: GMI, AMSR2 and SSMIS. (b) CrIS hyperspectral infrared sounder. The red and green lines represent experiment results for July 2023 and January 2024, respectively.

Fig. 2: 3-hour cumulative precipitation [mm]. (a) Forecast without window channels. (b) Forecast with window channels. (c) Forecast difference resulting from window channel assimilation: (b) – (a). (d) Radar/raingauge-analyzed precipitation data. The forecast time is 3 hours from 15 UTC on 7th July 2023.

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Implementing Isochoric-Isobaric Transformations in the MCV Model's Dynamic-Physical Coupling

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1. Introduction

Dynamic-physical coupling in atmospheric models enables accurate characterization of multi-scale atmospheric interactions through the integration of dynamic and physical processes. The design of the coupling strategy directly influences energy conservation, the efficiency of physical feedbacks, and the coordination of multi-scale interactions. The accuracy of coupling processes further affects the enhancement of simulation and the stability of runtime performance (Gross et al., 2018). Beljaars et al. (2004) demonstrated that improved numerical coupling mechanisms within dynamic-physical interactions lead to a reduction in prediction errors. The next-generation regional/global unified nonhydrostatic Multi-moment Constrained finite Volume (MCV) model by CMA (Li et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2014; 2023), achieves efficient dynamic-physical coupling via innovative framework design. However, current MCV model still exhibits inherent biases in isochoric-isobaric coordinate thermodynamic conversion within the coupling process, which may result in imbalances in temperature tendencies, biases in precipitation simulations, and reduced predictability scores. To address this issue, this study aims to implement isochoric-isobaric transformations within the dynamic-physical coupling strategy of the MCV model.

2. Method and results

2.1 Isochoric-isobaric coupling method

The physics-dynamics coupling in MCV model differs from many existing atmospheric models in that it is performed at constant volume (density) rather than constant pressure. However, the physical parameterization schemes is built at pressure-based coordinates. Thermodynamically, this corresponds to the dynamic core being associated with an isochoric process and the physical processes with an isobaric process. During dynamics-physics coupling, the update of temperature tendencies must incorporate the conversion between these two distinct thermodynamic processes to ensure heat conservation. Previously, the MCV model's coupling scheme lacked consideration of this conversion, resulting in biases in the potential temperature fed back to the dynamic core following physical process computations. This, in turn, led to systematic underestimation of total and grid-scale precipitation in tropical regions. To address this issue, we redesigned the temperature conversion based on energy conservation and thermodynamic principles. Remember that total heat must be strictly conserved, then the dynamical temperature tendency that fed back from physics becomes

$$\Delta Q_{\text{dyn}} = \Delta Q_{\text{phy}} \implies \Delta T_{\text{dyn}} = \frac{c_p}{c_{vm}} \Delta T_{\text{phy}} \quad (1)$$

where Q represents the heat per mass, T is temperature, $c_{p\hat{A}}$ and $c_{vm\hat{A}}$ are specific capacity at constant pressure and moist specific capacity at constant volume, respectively.

2.2 Results and analysis

Case simulations implementing the dynamics-physics conversion formulation (1) demonstrate that, under identical resolution and initial conditions, total precipitation and grid-scale precipitation exhibit enhanced physical reasonableness (Fig. 1 a), with biases in temperature and humidity throughout the atmospheric column significantly reduced (figure

not shown). Supplementary analysis of vertical profiles of cloud water, rainwater, cloud ice, snow, and graupel reveals consistent improvements in precipitation forecasts, with hydrometeor particle predictions displaying enhanced physical consistency across all species (figures not shown). Furthermore, the optimized isochoric-isobaric conversion in dynamics-physics coupling has markedly mitigated the prior imbalance between dynamic and physical tendencies. After modification, the total temperature tendency exhibits improved balance, with the net temperature tendency in the lower atmosphere approaching zero in comparison with an approximate magnitude of 0.8°C per day in the pre-modification model (Fig. 1 b).

Figure 1. (a) Zonal mean of 24-hour accumulated total precipitation and grid-scale precipitation. (b) Temperature tendencies from dynamics and various physical processes in the MCV model forecasts (24-48h) averaged over the tropical region (20°S - 20°N). Dot line shows pre-modification results, solid line indicates the post-modification results.

3. Summary

Following the implementation of isochoric-isobaric transformations at the coupling interface, the MCV model exhibits improved energy conservation. Additionally, the ratio of grid-scale to convective precipitation is rendered more physically consistent, while biases in temperature and water vapor distributions are mitigated. Furthermore, predictability lead times are extended in both the Northern Hemisphere and the Southern Hemisphere.

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Numerical experiments on snow particle characteristics in Furano, Japan

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1. Introduction

Quantitative evaluation of snowfall is important for assessing disaster risks such as traffic disruptions, snow avalanches, and falling snow from rooftops. Beyond quantity, other characteristics of snowfall—such as the shape, density, and number concentration of snow particles—are a major cause of uncertainty when evaluating snowfall intensity using weather radar. These properties also influence specific types of snow avalanches, affect visibility, and are potential factors in determining snow quality satisfaction for sports like skiing and snowboarding. In Furano city, Hokkaido, Japan, businesses and local governments have launched the Furano bonchi powder project, collaborating with universities and research institutes to objectively predict local powder snow conditions and communicate this information to skiers and snowboarders. This report presents the preliminary results of an investigation into the mechanisms of snowfall formation in the area using a numerical weather prediction model.

Figure 1: (a) Computational domains for the numerical simulations. Domains 1 and 2 correspond to the 5km- and 1.2km-NHM simulations, respectively. The white frame in the map of Domain 2 indicates the area shown in Fig. 3. White circles show the locations of Sapporo and Furano cities. The black line indicates the administrative boundary of Furano city, part of which follows the western mountain ridge. (b) Simulated precipitation amount accumulated from 0300 JST on January 1st to 0800 JST on January 3rd, 2023. Colored circles indicate observation results by the JMA's AMeDAS.

2. Numerical experiments

A numerical simulation system was established based on the Japan Meteorological Agency's Non-Hydrostatic Model (JMA-NHM, Saito et al., 2006). It used a double-moment bulk cloud microphysics scheme to predict both the mixing ratio and concentration of particles for all hydrometeor classes (i.e., cloud water, rain, cloud ice, snow, and graupel). Simulations were conducted successively once a day, shifting the initial time in 24-hour steps from December 31, 2022, to January 2, 2023. Each simulation started with a 5 km horizontal resolution (5km-NHM) over a 2500 km \times 2500 km domain (Domain 1, as shown in Fig. 1a). This was followed by a nested simulation at a 1.2 km horizontal resolution (1.2km-NHM) in a 600 km \times 600 km domain (Domain 2). The 5km-NHM simulation used initial and boundary conditions obtained from the JMA's mesoscale analysis data (MANAL). The initial time was 1500 JST (UTC+9) daily, with boundary conditions provided every 3 hours. The 1.2km-NHM simulation obtained its initial and boundary conditions from the 5km-NHM output. Its initial time was 6 hours later than the 5km-NHM run, and boundary conditions were

provided every hour. The process tracking method (Hashimoto et al., 2020) was applied in the 1.2km-NHM simulation to reveal contributions of microphysical processes to surface snowfall.

3. Results and summary

Figure 1b shows the simulated precipitation amount from 0300 JST on January 1st to 0800 JST on January 3rd, 2023. the northwest winter monsoon brought snow clouds from the Sea of Japan, leading to snowfall across Hokkaido. The simulation results exhibit good agreement with observations from the Japan Meteorological Agency's Automated Meteorological Data Acquisition System (AMeDAS, colored circles). Figure 2a displays the distribution of hourly snowfall across the coast and inland areas of Hokkaido. Figures 2b and 2c illustrate that the contributions of depositional growth of solid hydrometeors reached Furano after passing the western mountain ridge. However, the contribution of riming growth did not reach Furano, as depicted in Figure 2d. These findings suggest that snowfall over the Furano basin is likely composed of pristine snow crystals or aggregates thereof. Our simulation results align with the conclusions of Harimaya and Kanemura (1975), who found that the riming process is less predominant in the inland areas of Hokkaido compared to the coastal areas.

The contribution of the riming process is an important factor in determining the characteristics of snow particles, which may affect the snow quality experienced by skiers and snowboarders visiting Furano. This study is currently limited to a single-case analysis. The author plans to increase the number of cases and continue the analysis in the future by incorporating the effects of snow metamorphism processes.

Acknowledgements

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Figure 2: (a) Hourly precipitation amount averaged over the period from 0300 JST, January 1st to 0300 JST, January 4th, 2023. (b) Same as (a), but showing the contribution of depositional growth of solid hydrometeors in the temperature range of -10 to -20 °C, *excluding* conditions where the temperature is -14 to -17 °C and the ice supersaturation is $\geq 7\%$. (c) Same as (b), but for the temperature range of -20 to -36 °C. (d) Same as (a), but showing the contribution of riming growth of solid hydrometeors. The thin black contour shows the topography.

4

Parameterization of physical processes in Earth System Models or their components

The impact of the mixing length constraint on tropical cyclone simulations of HAFS

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Introduction

The planetary boundary layer (PBL) is crucial for regulating the exchange of momentum, heat, and water vapor between the atmosphere and ocean surface. Therefore, an accurate PBL parameterization is essential for simulating tropical cyclone (TC) track and intensity within the Hurricane Analysis and Forecast System (HAFS). Mixing length, a key variable in PBL schemes, characterizes mixing scales. Research has shown that TC simulations, particularly regarding intensity, are sensitive to both the formulations and constraints of mixing length. These are common options for adjusting TC simulations. Strobach (2022, WAF) also demonstrated that mixing length formulations and their constraints significantly impact vertical profiles over land in the FV3 model. This paper will present an experiment using an idealized HAFS (Wang et al., 2024) to illustrate the impact of mixing length constraints on TC intensity forecasts. A new constraint formulation is also proposed and tested.

Experiment setup

The current operational HAFS employs a TKE-Based Eddy-Diffusivity Mass-Flux (EDMF) parameterization to model sub-grid vertical mixing. The eddy diffusivity is modelled as a product of a velocity scale and mixing length (L). The mixing length itself is derived using a parcel method, as proposed by Bougeault and Lacarrere (1989). To prevent unrealistic estimations of L due to inherent simplifications, constraints are usually applied. In the current EDMF scheme adopted in HAFS, the mixing length is capped at a constant value (Lmax). In HAFS simulations, the selection of Lmax is dependent on whether it can reduce errors and biases in model intensity and TC size. For instance, Lmax is set to 250 meters in HFSA, while it is limited to 75 meters in HFSA. Ideally, Lmax should be carefully selected to be neither excessively large nor small. Its purpose is to constrain unrealistic estimates without compromising reasonable ones. High sensitivity to Lmax might indicate the Lmax is too small or many L estimates are unrealistic. To demonstrate HAFS's sensitivity to Lmax, we run it with varying Lmax values.

An idealized HAFS configuration (Wang et al. 2024) is used to run the experiment. The configuration is the same as that of the atmosphere component of the operational HAFS, except for the idealized initial and boundary conditions. Lmax values of 100 m, 200 m, and 300 m are used in the idealized simulations.

Fig. 1. Time series of (a) Vmax, (b) R34, and (c)R50.

Results

Figure 1a shows that a simulated TC with Lmax=100 rapidly intensifies at hour 60, with the maximum 10-m wind (Vmax) increasing from 100 kt to 150 kt within 24 hours. In contrast, TCs with Lmax=200m and 300m exhibit similar Vmax time series, which do not show this rapid intensification and remain 20-30 kt weaker (Figs. 1 b & c). The TC simulated with Lmax=100m exhibits the smallest R34 and R50 (radii of 34kt and 50kt wind speeds,

respectively). The azimuthal distributions of the median L values at hour 96 from the three simulations are presented in Figure 2. The maximum median L values are 87, 133, and 143 m for Lmax settings of 100, 200, and 300m, respectively. These comparisons suggest that HAFS simulations demonstrate reduced sensitivity to Lmax when it exceeds 200m. Below 200m (e.g., 100m), the model's length scales are more frequently constrained. An Lmax of 200m or greater provides a sufficient constraint for TC simulations.

Fig. 2. Azimuthal distributions of median L of HAFS simulations using Lmax of (a)100m, (b)200m, and (c) 300m.

To assess the L values in TC simulations, Figure 3(a) illustrates the distribution of L values derived using the momentum fluxes and gradients from a large eddy simulation of a TC with 33m grid spacing. The figure indicates that L values are greater within the PBL in TC eyewall regions, and these values significantly exceed those employed in HAFS simulations. To address this discrepancy, we suggest that Lmax is proportional to the PBL height, exhibiting a similar distribution pattern of L to that derived from LES, though the values are still smaller. To address this discrepancy, we propose that Lmax is proportional to the PBL height. This would lead to an L distribution pattern that more closely resembles LES-derived patterns than those obtained with constant Lmax values (Fig. 2), even though the values themselves are still lower than those derived from LES. Figure 1 (green lines) shows the simulated TC with the new Lmax intensifying to 150 kt at the 80th hr, with increased R34 and R50.

Fig. 3. Azimuthal distributions of median L from (a) LES, (b) HAFS with proposed new Lmax.

Summary

TC simulations exhibit reduced sensitivity to Lmax when it exceeds 200 m. A newly proposed Lmax, which is dependent on PBL height, results in an L distribution that more closely matches those derived from a large eddy simulation. Further real-case simulations are currently underway.

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A Simplified Lake Model for Seasonal Prediction

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1. Abstract

The reproducibility of interannual variations in the lower atmosphere and the conditions of land surfaces with which it interacts are important in seasonal prediction. To enhance related data over previous JMA seasonal prediction systems (which relied on monthly climatology for lake-related variables such as surface water temperature and ice concentration), a lake model was introduced into the system (CPS3; Hirahara et al. 2023) and modified in the next iteration (CPS4; Kubo et al. 2025). As variability in air temperature above lakes is high in winter and closely associated with ice presence, particular emphasis is placed on the treatment of lake ice. Accordingly, the lake model predicts only lake surface conditions and lake ice variables required as the lower boundary for the atmospheric model, and is highly efficient in operational usage. Since there is no entire-lake targeting, lake depth data are not required; only monthly climatology for surface temperatures (which are based on satellite observation and therefore considered highly accurate) are needed. The model helps to make data on the amplitude of interannual variations in surface air temperature over lakes more realistic.

2. Lake Model Overview

Based on vertical column thermodynamics, the model predicts lake ice formation and variations in water temperature throughout water phase changes and heat transfer among water, ice, and snow. It consists of three layers of lake water, four layers of lake ice and one layer of snow on lake ice. Water, ice and snow densities are constant, and the water temperature in the bottom (third) layer is set as a constant annual-mean climatology value because lower water temperature changes little throughout the year. The energy of water's upper two layers, lake ice and snow on lake ice is conserved, but the variability of lake water mass is not taken into account. The thickness of lake water layer is constant. The thermal diffusion coefficient between the first and second layers is set to be globally uniform as the inverse of an arbitrary relaxation time. This time between the second and third layers depends on the observed amplitude of the seasonal cycle in surface temperature, with shorter relaxation times associated with shallow lake conditions. The seasonal amplitude is defined as the difference between the maximum and minimum climatology monthly mean surface temperature based on MODIS/Terra Land Surface Temperature data (MOD11C3_v006; Wan, Z. et al, 2015). The bottom water temperature is set to a proportional value between the annual mean of the observed surface temperature and the temperature where the density of water reaches its maximum (3.98°C), as bottom water temperature is close to the annual minimum in non-frozen lakes and the maximum water density temperature in frozen lakes. The model uses a fixed water density, and the annual mean (rather than the annual minimum) is applied. Thus, it acts in a pendulum-like manner, unlike the thermostat behavior observed around the annual minimum value, or 3.98°C in nature. The number of lake ice layers is constant, and the upper and lower limits of ice thickness are set individually to keep the upper layers thinner than the lower ones. Lake ice concentration and thickness vary independently during freezing and melting, respectively, enabling representation of both wide/thin and narrow/thick conditions.

3. CPS4 Enhancements

In CPS3, a lower limit of 0°C was set for the observed monthly mean temperature for calculation of annual mean and seasonal amplitudes. This limit is removed in CPS4, resulting in larger lake ice indications due to the lower annual mean temperature and larger seasonal amplitude in frozen lakes. Bottom water temperature has also been modified to the average of the annual mean and annual minimum, resulting in higher water temperature indications in ice-free lakes such as the Caspian Sea.

4. Results

Figure 1 shows seasonal changes in interannual surface air temperature variation on the Great Lakes. Variability is large for Nov. – Mar. in reanalysis (JRA-55; Kobayashi et al. 2015). Application of the lake model enables appropriate lake ice representation, with amplitudes of interannual variation much closer to those of JRA-55 than those of climatology lake ice. Figure 2 shows seasonal surface air temperature biases relative to reanalysis (JRA-3Q; Kosaka et al. 2024) and the effects of model enhancement. Warm biases for North America and Siberia in boreal winter and cold biases in the Caspian Sea are reduced.

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Figure 1: Monthly interannual variation of surface air temperature on the Great Lakes in (a) climatology lake ice and (b) the lake model. Colored lines represent model results for initial data, and black lines represent JRA-55.

Figure 2: (a) Climatological mean fields of surface air temperatures (contours) and biases relative to JRA-3Q (shading) with the current lake model, and (b) effects of enhancements in CPS4 for boreal summer. (c) and (d): as per (a) and (b) but for boreal winter.

5

Forecast verification; novel methodologies to diagnose and measure systematic errors

Power Spectra Verification of Machine Learning Weather Prediction

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Efficient yet meaningful verification for comparing machine learning weather prediction (MLWP) against traditional physics-based numerical weather prediction (NWP) is crucial for scientific credibility and operational uptake. Traditional summary statistics, like MSE, bias, variance or correlations alone, can be hedged by smoother forecasts or climatology-induced false skill (Hamill and Juras, 2006). Moreover, traditional metrics can mask unphysical behaviors and canceling errors. Power spectra diagnostics have been recently leveraged, to enable scale-aware physically meaningful evaluation of both MLWP and NWP models (e.g. Husain et al, 2025; Rodwell et al, 2025). This note wishes to highlight some of the key features of the power-spectra diagnostic approaches, with recommendations for operational verification practices.

The diagnostic capabilities of the power-spectra verification statistics are illustrated for global forecasts from the Environment and Climate Change Canada’s (ECCC) operational NWP-based Global Deterministic Prediction System (GDPS) and two other ECCC experimental systems: the GEML (Global Environmental eMuLator) MLWP model, and the hybrid NWP-MLWP system based on Spectral Nudging (GDPS-SN). Predictions from all these systems are verified against the operational GDPS analysis.

Figure 1: (Left) Forecast activity ratio as a function of lead time and (right) 120-h spectral activity ratio for 500-hPa geopotential height anomalies for (black) the GDPS analysis, (blue) GDPS, (red) GDPS-SN and (gray) GEML, averaged over 60 cases of JFM 2022.

Figure 2: Spectral activity ratio of 72-h screen-level temperature for GDPS (blue) and GEML (red), averaged over 62 cases of JJA 2022. The ratio is shown for the stationary JJA 2022 sample climatology (dotted), transient anomalies (dashed) and the total/integral screen-level temperature fields (solid).

Climatology and anomalies: Atmospheric fields from the global forecasts and verifying analysis are separated into transient anomalies and stationary climatology, by subtracting the ERA5 30-year climatology. This enables focusing on weather phenomena and removing artificial skill due to persistent climatological features.

Power Spectral Decomposition: Gridded atmospheric fields are decomposed spectrally using truncated spherical harmonic expansions (e.g., up to $n=800$ for $\sim 0.25^\circ$ resolution). This spectral representation enables evaluation as a function of total

wavenumber (n), corresponding to physical scales ($L = 2\pi R/n$). Such scale decomposition is critical for determining the forecast "effective resolution" and diagnosing compensating errors at different scales. Furthermore, spectral decomposition permits the assessment of bias, error, and skill at different scales separately (e.g. Casati et al, 2023).

In verification, **bias and accuracy/skill** are key and complementary *attributes* of the forecast *quality*: the bias compares forecast-versus-observation marginal distributions, whereas the accuracy pertains to the forecast-observation joint distribution (Jolliffe and Stephenson, 2012). In the power spectra framework, these attributes can be assessed by computing forecast and analysis variances and their covariance.

Activity and coherence: the *activity*, defined as the standard deviation of the anomalies, is associated with the amount (and intensity) of active weather (Ben Bouallègue et al, 2024). The forecast versus analysis *activity ratio* is a measure of the *marginal bias* in the forecast-versus-analysis variability, or of the *amplitude error* for the spherical harmonics. The anomaly correlation (named *coherence* for the power spectra) can provide a complementary measure of accuracy/skill (or *phase error* in spectral space). When evaluated for the spectral components, activity ratio and coherence can assess scale-dependent bias/amplitude errors and accuracy/skill for each spatial scale, separately. While in this short note we illustrate solely the activity ratio, measures of both bias and accuracy/skill should always be evaluated in tandem, to provide a more complete assessment of forecast performance (e.g. Figure 2 of Husain et al, 2025).

Figure 1 shows that the seemingly almost neutral bias of GEML when the activity ratio is evaluated on the anomaly fields only (left), is affected by unphysical compensating effects on meso- α and meso- β scales, which are detected solely when using power-spectral diagnostics (right). **Figure 2** shows that the spectral activity ratio captures GEML variance deficiency for mesoscales, typical of the overly smooth ML model outputs. Moreover, the stationary versus transient signal separation reveals that GEML resolves well the climatological (stationary) variability, but that this compensates for a large negative bias associated with the transient anomalies. This is an expected behavior for any MLWP model trained to minimize MSE, which leads to fine-scale smoothing to reduce the "double penalty" effect (Subich et al, 2025).

In conclusion, for operational verification practices we recommend: i) computing both activity ratio and anomaly correlation to assess marginal bias/amplitude error and forecast skill/accuracy; ii) separate stationary climatology from transient anomalies, to distinguish skill in reproducing climate versus actual weather; iii) apply spectral decomposition to analyze separately the distinct model behaviors at different scales, to detect unphysical error compensation, and to assess the "effective resolution", particularly for deterministic ML models that are prone to smoothing.

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6

Uncoupled and coupled data assimilation for integrated earth system analysis and prediction; methodology and data impact sensitivity studies

Update of the Radiative Transfer Model to RTTOV-13 in JMA's NWP Systems

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1. Introduction

Various types of satellite radiance data are assimilated to determine accurate initial conditions for numerical weather prediction (NWP) models. The RTTOV fast radiative transfer model (Eyre 1991), developed by the EUMETSAT Satellite Application Facility on Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP SAF), is used as the observation operator for assimilating satellite radiance data in JMA's NWP systems (Global, meso-scale and local NWP). As a first step in updating RTTOV10.2 (Saunders et al. 2012) to RTTOV-13 (Saunders et al. 2020), the minimal changes necessary to ensure secure implementation with no significant impact on NWP accuracy (such as changes to modules and relevant file formats) were made in 2022. The optical depth coefficient files (referred to here simply as "coefficient files") and sea surface emissivity models in RTTOV were subsequently updated to the new versions, and relevant quality control procedures were adjusted accordingly. This report briefly summarizes the effects of the changes on NWP systems.

2. Modification of Quality Control Procedures

The coefficient files for sensors already in use were updated to Version 13 other than for CrIS, which showed no enhancement from coefficient file updating.

Sea surface emissivity models (FASTEM-6 (Kazumori and English 2015) for microwave observation and IREMIS for infrared observation) are now available in RTTOV13. FASTEM-6 models the dependence of sea surface emissivity on relative wind direction (RWD) more appropriately. Global analysis indicated smaller O-B (observation minus background; i.e., the difference between observed and calculated brightness temperature) biases in microwave imagers dependent on RWD. However, biases dependent on surface wind speed were larger for surface-sensitive channels of AMSU-A and ATMS. Accordingly, surface wind speed was added as a predictor in variational bias correction (VarBC) for ch4 and ch5 of AMSU-A and ch6 of ATMS. FASTEM-6 was not adopted in meso-scale and local analysis because no enhancement was observed in relation to a FASTEM update from version 4 to 6 and addition of surface wind speed as a predictor in VarBC.

The statistical characteristics of calculated brightness temperature changed as a result of the updates to the coefficient files and the sea surface emissivity models described above. The static scan bias correction value and the precipitation screening parameters for AMSU-A, which were estimated in advance from statistics on observed and calculated brightness temperature, were updated for the new calculation characteristics. Retrieved cloud water amounts for AMSU-A quality control are also larger than before, mainly due to the updating of scan bias correction values. As a result, the amount of data considered to represent cloud increased, and the amount of data used decreased. In reference to O-B statistics, the threshold of cloud water content used for cloud detection was increased from 100 to 120 g/m² to make the number of data used comparable to that before the update.

3. Effects of Updating Coefficient Files and Sea Surface Emissivity Models on NWP Systems

Data assimilation experiments were conducted to evaluate the effects of updating the coefficient files and sea surface emissivity models to the new versions in JMA's NWP systems. This report details the results of experiments in the global NWP system for the periods from June to October 2023 and November 2023 to March 2024. The control experiments (CNTL) had the same configuration as JMA's operational global NWP system as of March 2025, and the test experiments (TEST) were as per CNTL except for the modifications described in Section 2.

Figure 1 shows changes in the standard deviation and mean of FG departures (another expression of O-B) for radiosonde temperature against CNTL. Those of TEST were closer to observations than CNTL, which indicates an enhanced first guess for the temperature field. Meanwhile, negative biases in 500 hPa

geopotential height against radiosonde observations over the tropics in CNTL showed a slightly increased tendency in TEST (Figure 2). This change corresponded closely to that in the O-B of ATMS ch6 (not shown), which was likely the result of a bug fix affecting sensors that have channels influenced by the 184 GHz ozone absorption line (Saunders et al. 2017). The results for precipitation forecasts and tropical cyclone track and intensity forecasts were almost neutral. Experiments with meso-scale and local NWP systems showed no significant changes in forecast accuracy.

4. Summary

Updating for the coefficient files and sea surface emissivity models of RTTOV to the new version in JMA's NWP systems showed an almost neutral effect on NWP, while stratospheric temperature fields were enhanced in the global NWP system. The modification was implemented in the meso-scale and local NWP systems in March 2025, and is scheduled for implementation in the global NWP system in autumn 2025.

Figure 1: (a) Ratios of change [%] in the standard deviation of FG departures for radiosonde temperature observation. Error bars show confidence levels of 95%. (b) Mean of FG departures [K] for radiosonde temperature observation. Solid and dotted lines represent the results of TEST and CNTL experiments. Red and green lines represent the results of summer and winter experiments.

Figure 2: Mean error of 500 hPa geopotential height [gpm] in 1-day forecasting against radiosonde observations. (a) represents CNTL results, and (b) represents differences between TEST and CNTL.

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Updating Surface Humidity Observation Error in JMA's Regional NWP Systems

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1. Introduction

Water vapor in the lower troposphere has a significant influence on the occurrence and development of torrential rainfall caused by stationary linear mesoscale convective systems. Accordingly, assimilation of observation data that capture the inflow of such vapor is critical for optimal torrential-rain forecasting. In this context, the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) began progressively installing hygrometers at its Automated Meteorological Data Acquisition System (AMeDAS) facilities on a national basis in March 2020. JMA assimilates screen-level relative humidity as observed by these hygrometers into its regional NWP systems (mesoscale and local; JMA, 2025). As statistical examination of these hygrometers indicated a tendency for reduced observation accuracy under high-humidity conditions, JMA applied modification to increase the observation error of surface specific humidity under these conditions to its regional NWP systems in February 2025.

This report describes findings on hygrometer data quality and observation error characteristics, along with related effects on regional NWP systems.

2. Hygrometer Data Quality

The Rotronic MP-102H and Vaisala HMP155 hygrometers deployed at AMeDAS stations differ in measurement characteristics due to structural variations, such as heater functionality and distinct internal processing specifications. Statistical comparison of humidity data from these instruments showed that the MP-102H frequently records 100% relative humidity (RH), whereas the HMP155 rarely does so (Fig. 1). This is often seen with the MP-102H at stations near rice paddies or other consistently humid areas. In contrast, the HMP155 rarely exceeds 97% RH, even during rainfall or similar conditions. In dry conditions, such as sunny daytime periods, both instruments show similar readings. These differences suggest that the data characteristics of AMeDAS hygrometers vary significantly in high-humidity conditions, indicating larger observation uncertainties.

3. Update of Observation Error Settings

As AMeDAS hygrometers still provide useful data despite lower accuracy in humid conditions, it is deemed appropriate to utilize these data while accounting for the shortcomings. Accordingly, a method is applied to increase the observation error of surface specific humidity when RH exceeds 90%.

The error is currently set as 0.7 – 0.75 g/kg (equivalent to approximately 3.6 – 3.8% RH at 25°C) for the regional NWP system. In the mesoscale NWP system, the standard deviation of climatological forecast error for the first model layer over land during summer is approximately 5% RH. Considering the larger observation error in high-humidity conditions and the representativeness error of water vapor, the observation error at 100% RH was set at three times the current value – roughly twice the model forecast error. The observation error increases in linear progression from the current value at 90% to three times the current value at 100%.

4. Effects on Analysis and Prediction

To evaluate the effects of the updated observation error settings on regional NWP systems, numerical experiments were conducted based on the system as of March 2023 (CNTL) with updated observation error settings (TEST) for June 26 – July 25, 2023. In the mesoscale NWP system, increasing the observation error in high-humidity conditions mitigated the initial bias of surface specific humidity and reduced root mean square errors (RMSEs) (Fig. 2). In precipitation prediction, false alarms for light rain decreased, leading to enhanced equitable threat scores (ETS). In the local NWP system, the initial dry bias of surface specific humidity was mitigated, while effects on precipitation and other elements were small.

5. Summary

The study suggested that JMA’s AMeDAS hygrometers exhibit lower accuracy in high humidity. By increasing the observation error settings for such conditions, accuracy for surface specific humidity and precipitation forecasts in the mesoscale NWP system was enhanced. JMA implemented these changes in its regional NWP systems in February 2025.

Figure 1: Observation frequency distribution of relative humidity by instrument type based on statistics from March 10 2023 to February 29 2024. (a) Rotronic MP-102H (157 stations), (b) Vaisala HMP155 (208 stations).

Figure 2: Mean errors and RMSEs for observation of specific humidity [g/kg] over the experiment period of June 26 – July 25 2023 in the mesoscale NWP system. Blue lines: CNTL; red lines: TEST.

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Developments in ocean, sea-ice, and wave modeling

MOM6-CICE6 Forecasting using the Unified Forecast System-Weather Model Framework

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Introduction

The operational Real Time Ocean Forecast System (RTOFS) version 2.5 is a global ocean-ice model with 1/12° resolution consisting of the HYCOM ocean model, the CICE4 ice model, and RTOFS-DA, an EMC version of a three-dimensional variational data analysis system, based on Cummings and Smedstad (2013). RTOFS is forced by wind and fluxes from the NCEP GDAS/GFS systems. RTOFSv2.5 includes climatological constraint adjustments in the temperature and salinity from the direct method for assimilation of Sea Surface Height (SSH), to prevent model drift. Assimilated observations include satellite Sea Surface Temperature (SST) retrievals from METOP and NOAA, satellite Sea Surface Salinity (SSS) retrievals from SMOS and SMAP, in-situ profiles of temperature and salinity from Argo, XBTs, gliders, and animal-borne sensors, in-situ SST and SSS from ships, drifters and moorings, Absolute Dynamic Topography (ADT) from altimetry, and satellite sea ice concentration retrievals from AMSR2 and SSMI/S. Future upgrades of RTOFS will include MOM6 and CICE6, coupled through the Unified Forecast System Weather Model (UFS-WM) framework. We present results for a first prototype for RTOFS 3.0 obtained with MOM6-CICE6 coupled through UFS-WM, and RTOFS-DA assimilation.

Simulations and Results

A UFS-WM MOM6-CICE6-RTOFS-DA simulation (MOM6 in what follows) was run with most of the assimilation features of RTOFS v2.5 (HYCOM). The MOM6 simulation was initialized from RTOFS for April 1, 2025, and cycled for the month of April. The atmospheric forcing was not identical to RTOFS, and sea ice concentration was not assimilated in CICE6. The same observations were assimilated in MOM6 and in HYCOM, but MOM6 did not use the First Guess at Appropriate Time method for hourly surface fields.

Fig. 1. Verification of temperature and salinity vs Argo: horizontal global average of Innovations (Observations minus Forecast, O-F) as a function of depth and time.

Vertical sections of Argo temperature and salinity observations minus forecast (O-F) biases for MOM6 and HYCOM are shown in Figure 1. MOM6 temperature biases improve with time, with the greatest improvements at ~200m depth. MOM salinity biases show reduced errors at depths > 200m. MOM6 then results in an improvement in global Argo verification with respect to HYCOM. MOM6 24-hr forecast SSH fields interpolated to along-track ADT observation locations for the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio regions are shown in Figure 2. The model forecast

SSH agrees well with altimeter ADT observations, with some localized differences at the location of the Gulf Stream front, and to a smaller degree at the Kuroshio front.

Fig. 2. SSH MOM6 verification: along track ADT observations (blue), 24 hour model forecast (red), and Innovations (O-F, green). The average difference between observations and model along each track was removed to correct for model-data geoid discrepancies.

Figure 3 shows the surface SSH, SST, SSS fields in MOM6 and HYCOM for the Gulf Stream region on 30 April 2025. The Gulf Stream SSH for both MOM6 and HYCOM agree well with SSH derived from ADT through a 2-DVar analysis of observations only. A vertical Atlantic meridional section of temperature (Fig. 3) shows smoother, more evenly distributed layer interfaces in MOM6, an improvement versus HYCOM. MOM6 also shows a less intense eddy field in MOM6, with less noise in SST and SSS.

Fig. 3. Gulf Stream region SSH, SST, SSS for MOM6, HYCOM, and an ADT 2-Dvar analysis from observations only (3 left panels), and Atlantic 50W meridional section of temperature for MOM6 and HYCOM (right panels).

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Upgrade of the Real-Time Ocean Forecast System to version 2.5

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Introduction

Real-Time Ocean Forecast System (RTOFS) is an ocean and sea ice prediction system configured at a horizontal resolution of 0.08°, with 41 hybrid vertical coordinate layers. The ocean model is the Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model ([HYCOM](#)) and the sea ice model is the Community Ice CodE version 4 ([CICE4](#)). In-situ profiles and surface observations of temperature and salinity, satellite retrievals of the Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and Sea Surface Salinity (SSS), Absolute Dynamic Topography (ADT) and sea ice concentrations are assimilated daily (i.e., 1-day data assimilation window) to obtain initial conditions for forecasts up to 8-days for the sea ice and ocean fields. The output comprises of hourly 2D surface fields and 3-hourly 3D fields.

Following is a summary of the changes implemented in a recent update of RTOFS to [version 2.5 on July 29, 2025](#); a description of the previous RTOFS versions can be found in Garraffo et al., 2020 and Cummings et al., 2021.

RTOFS v2.5

The version 2.5 upgrade included two major items. The first item addresses a problem with v2.4, which developed unrealistic salinity in the Caribbean Sea, depicted in Figure 1. This issue was addressed by the addition of constraints to the temperature and salinity (T&S) increments from the assimilation of ADT data. The constraints were derived from the climatology of T&S and applied based on weights that follow climatological variability in such a way that there are no adjustments where there is a high variability/uncertainty in the Sea Surface Height (SSH); for example, in the western boundary currents. Otherwise, the ADT is assimilated following a version of the Cooper and Haines (1996) methodology; see Garraffo et al., 2020.

The second major item was the addition of new sources of data that provide important constraints to the Data Assimilation (DA) output. Satellite SST from the Meteosat (MSG02 and MSG03), NOAA-21 and ADT from the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT, nadir orbits) were added and [BUFR](#) decoders of in-situ saildrone, glider and Argo profiles, marine mammals and ocean climate stations were also updated.

Fig. 1: December 1, 2024 00Z, salinity at 150 m depth in the Caribbean Sea. RTOFS v2.4 (left), Climatology (middle; monthly mean), RTOFS v2.5 (right). The salinity maximum is present (absent) in the v2.5 (v2.4). Existence and maintenance of this high salinity is important for forecasts, particularly hurricane forecasts using the Hurricane Analysis and Forecasting System ([HAFS](#)). HAFS forecasts are generated using a coupled model; the ocean initial conditions are from RTOFS.

Forecast improvements

The improvements in salinity persist during forecasts as well. A comparison of the root-mean-squared error of the forecast minus analysis for v2.4 and v2.5 (forecasts compared with their corresponding analyses) for Nov 15- Dec 24, 2024 shows clear improvements in both temperature and salinity at all depths; the plots at 150 m only are shown in Fig 2.

Fig. 2: RMSE of the forecast minus analysis for days 1 and 8 from forecasts during 2024/11/15- 12/24 at 150 m depth for the North Atlantic basin. Top (bottom) panels are for salinity (temperature). The left (right) panels are for RTOFS v2.4 (v2.5). Plots for other depths show similar improvements (not shown).

Summary

In comparison to RTOFS v2.4, the updated v2.5 provides an improved representation of the 3D ocean state for any given day. It also maintains improved skill for the entire duration of RTOFS forecasts (i.e., 8-days). RTOFS data can be downloaded from [NCEP NOMADS](https://nomads.ncep.noaa.gov/) and/or [Amazon AWS](https://aws.amazon.com/).

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Reanalysis datasets and statistical post- processing

Comparison of annual average climatology of key oceanographic parameters in the Bay of Bengal and Arabian Sea

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1. Introduction

The Bay of Bengal (BoB) and Arabian Sea (AS) are adjacent sub-basins of the north Indian Ocean (NIO), with markedly different upper ocean stratification due to contrasting freshwater inputs and wind-driven mixing (5). The thermohaline structure of the NIO plays a pivotal role in regulating air–sea heat and moisture exchanges, which in turn influence the onset, intensity, and variability of the Indian monsoon (4, 5). To enhance our understanding of upper-ocean stability, vertical mixing processes, and their coupling with atmospheric circulation, a comprehensive climatology of parameters such as sea surface temperature (SST), salinity, mixed layer depth (MLD), isothermal layer depth (ILD), and barrier layer thickness (BLT) over the NIO is an essential prerequisite for the modelling community in developing ocean–atmosphere coupled models. In the present study, we compare the annual climatological thermohaline structure of BoB and AS.

2. Data and Methodology

Monthly gridded SST and salinity data from the ARMOR3D dataset (2) (Copernicus Marine Service) are used. The MLD is directly obtained, while the ILD is calculated as the depth where temperature decreases by 0.2 °C from the 10 m reference depth (Boyer et al., 2004). The BLT is then computed as (ILD – MLD) (1&6). Annual climatology is estimated by averaging the annual means of the variable over the period 1993–2022.

3. Results and Discussion

A comparative description of the annual climatology of SST, salinity, MLD, ILD, and BLT, considering their vertical, latitudinal, and longitudinal variations over the BoB and AS is provided below.

3.1 Vertical T–S Structure (Fig. 1) the annual climatology of surface salinity is lower in BOB than AS, as freshwater input through rainfall and river discharge markedly exceeds evaporation in BOB. In contrast, the evaporation exceeds precipitation and river discharge is limited in AS. The salinity increases with depth, showing a rapid rise in the upper 100 meters in BOB. In contrast, a slow increase to a subsurface maximum at ~75 meters, then a very gradual decrease below in AS. The annual temperature climatology is slightly warmer in BOB than AS at the surface, gradually decreasing with depth in both basins. This vertical T–S structure leads to a higher Brunt–Väisälä frequency in the BoB due to high surface layer stratification, supporting the development of a stable barrier layer (BL), that inhibits vertical mixing (3,6). The annual climatology of BOB and AS highlights following differences (corresponding values for AS are presented in parentheses): BLT: ~20 m (8m); MLD: ~20 m (29.6m); ILD: ~35 m (29.5m).

3.2 Latitudinal variation (Fig. 2) zonal average over the BoB and AS depicts SST's are warmer and surface salinity is lower in BOB than AS, north of 20°N, whereas, BoB SST's are cooler than the AS between 0°–20°N. The MLD remains shallower in the BoB than in the AS, while the ILD extends deeper in both basins, except from 0°–4°N. Notably, near the equator (0–5°N), MLD is deeper in BOB than the AS due to weaker freshwater stratification and stronger wind-driven mixing (3, 4, 6, and 8). BLT exhibits strong latitudinal variation in BOB, exceeding 20 m between 15–20°N due to freshwater input that enhances stratification, suppresses mixing, and results in a shallow MLD. Conversely, lower freshwater and stronger mixing in AS maintain a shallow BLT (0–10 m) across most latitudes, similar to earlier findings (1, 6). However, north of 20°N in the BoB, both the ILD and BLT approach zero due to limited bathymetric depth in near-coastal regions, where mixing dominates over stratification. The latitudinal gradient of SST, BLT, ILD and surface salinity are much stronger north of 20°N in BOB than AS, due large inflow of freshwater from precipitation and river runoff.

3.3 Longitudinal variation (Fig. 3) the meridional-averaged variation illustrate that SST's in BOB are warmer and surface salinity is less than in AS over all longitudes. SST's gradually increases from west to east in BoB

(5), while in AS, SST decreases from west to east in the western (40°-50°E) and eastern (72°-78°E) basin, while increases from west to east in the central 50°-72°E basin. The western AS (near 45°-50°E) is notably cooler than the eastern, due to strong winds causing upwelling in the summer monsoon (5). Surface salinity decreases eastward in BOB owing to freshwater input (4, 8). The AS is characterized by high surface salinity throughout, with slightly higher salinity in the east than in the west. The BoB is characterized by a distinct pattern: cooler (warmer) SSTs in the western (eastern) BoB correspond to higher (lower) salinity - a signature of freshwater-induced stratification. The ILD also deepens eastward, but variation with longitude is less than the MLD, resulting in a pronounced BL (BLT up to ~20-30 m) in the BoB and a very shallow BLT in the AS (6).

4. Conclusion

In the vertical T-S structure, the BoB has lower surface salinity and higher surface temperature than the AS, with salinity increasing and temperature decreasing more sharply with depth in the BoB. Across most latitudes, the MLD is shallower and the BLT is thicker in the BOB than in the AS, associated with lower surface salinity that enhances stratification and suppresses vertical mixing. The BOB exhibits a pronounced east-west contrast, with lower SST and higher salinity in the west than east. This zonal asymmetry in the thermal-haline structure promotes the formation of a substantially thicker BL (20-30 m) in the BoB. In contrast, the AS remains well-mixed with a consistently shallow BLT across all longitudes, lacking a pronounced BL. These results provide an updated baseline for understanding surface ocean stratification in the NIO.

Fig. 1: Annual climatological vertical variation of temperature, Salinity, MLD, ILD, and BLT averaged over BoB (solid) and AS (dashed).

Fig. 2: Annual climatological zonal variation of SST, surface Salinity, MLD, ILD, and BLT averaged over the BoB (solid) and AS (dashed).

Fig. 3: Annual climatological meridional variation of SST, Salinity, MLD, ILD, and BLT, averaged over the BoB (solid) and AS (dashed).

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Annual cycle of surface salinity, SST, precipitation, MLD and BLT: Comparison between Bay of Bengal and Arabian Sea

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1. Introduction

Seasonal variations in the North Indian Ocean (NIO) are driven by the interplay of sea surface salinity (SSS), sea surface temperature (SST), precipitation, and mixed layer dynamics, which together shape air–sea interactions and climate feedbacks. The Bay of Bengal (BoB) and Arabian Sea (AS), though part of the same monsoon system, respond differently to these drivers because of their contrasting freshwater inputs, evaporation–precipitation balance, and wind-driven mixing (Shenoi et al., 2002). These processes critically influence upper-ocean stratification, mixed layer depth (MLD), and barrier layer thickness (BLT), which are central to monsoon variability and regional climate (Rao & Sivakumar, 2003; de Boyer Montégut et al., 2007). This study examines the climatological annual cycle of key oceanic variables across BoB and AS, the two sub-regions of the NIO, using high-resolution satellite and reanalysis datasets, with emphasis on the seasonal evolution of MLD and BLT.

2. Data and Methodology

The weekly climatology is constructed using the following datasets:

SST: Daily $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ NOAA OISST v2.1, Precipitation: Daily $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ Global Precipitation Climatology Project (GPCP). Salinity and MLD: Weekly ARMOR3D Level 4 reanalysis (Copernicus Marine Service), and BLT: Computed as isothermal layer depth (ILD) – MLD, following the Boyer et al. (2004). ILD is estimated as the depth at which temperature decreases by 0.2°C from the 10 m reference depth. Two regions are defined for spatial averaging: **1. BoB:** $78^\circ\text{--}100^\circ\text{E}$, $0^\circ\text{--}25^\circ\text{N}$, **2. AS:** $40^\circ\text{--}78^\circ\text{E}$, $0^\circ\text{--}25^\circ\text{N}$. Each dataset is first averaged into weekly means for each year. Weekly climatology for each of the 53 weeks is then estimated by averaging weekly means across the entire period from 1993-2023.

3. Results and Discussion

The annual cycle of SSS, SST, precipitation, MLD and BLT over BoB and AS, based on the weekly climatology as illustrated in Figure 1, are compared and discussed below.

SSS: - In the BoB, SSS peaks during the pre-monsoon season, and then declines sharply as the summer monsoon intensifies due to heavy rainfall and river discharge (Shenoi et al. 2002), reaching a minimum in the post-monsoon. The AS remains more saline than the BoB year-round. The minimum SSS in AS is during the pre-monsoon, then increases through the monsoon season as evaporation exceeds precipitation, peaking in the post-monsoon when precipitation subsides and persists till winter.

SST: In the BoB, SST has annual minimum during winter and maximum in pre-monsoon. During the monsoon, SST declines gradually due to reduced solar insolation from increased cloud cover, enhanced latent heat loss from evaporation, and surface cooling from heavy precipitation (Rao & Sivakumar, 2003), and warm SST $>28^\circ\text{C}$ persists till post monsoon. Evaporation rates in the BoB are lower than in the AS, and the shallow MLD limits vertical mixing (Shenoi et al., 2002), facilitating relatively warm and stable SSTs through the post-monsoon. In the AS, SST has two peaks, one primary peak in the pre-monsoon and secondary peak during post monsoon, followed by minimum in winter. Stronger winds during the summer monsoon season cause deeper mixing, and substantially higher evaporation rates in AS than in the BoB, resulting in greater latent heat loss and a more pronounced cooling (Shenoi et al 2002).

Precipitation: - The precipitation increases sharply with the onset of the summer monsoon in late April to first week of May and maintained till post monsoon in both BoB and AS. SSTs above convective threshold ($>28^\circ\text{C}$) enhance evaporation causing increased atmospheric moisture, thereby creating favourable conditions for convection and rainfall (Gadgil, 2003). In the BoB, low SSS due to freshwater input strengthens surface stratification, and shallow MLD which in turn maintains these

warm SSTs during post monsoon seasons, resulting in more precipitation (Sprintall & Tomczak, 1992). A thick BLT reinforces this stability by trapping heat and moisture in the upper layer, providing sustained energy for deep convection and heavy precipitation (Sprintall & Tomczak, 1992; Thadathil et al., 2007). Thus, precipitation is more in BoB than AS throughout the year.

MLD: - In the BoB, the MLD is shallower than in the AS throughout the year. The seasonal evolution of the MLD in BoB is characterized by shoaling in winter and post monsoon, at its minimum in the pre-monsoon and subsequent deepening in the monsoon. However, the concurrent increase in BLT indicates that freshwater stratification from rainfall and river discharge keeps the effective MLD shallow (Sprintall & Tomczak, 1992; de Boyer Montégut 2007). In the AS, the MLD is deepest in winter due to convective overturning and surface cooling, shoals in the pre-monsoon, and then deepens again during the monsoon under wind-driven mixing (Shenoi et al 2002). This deep mixing entrains cooler, saltier subsurface water, lowering SSTs and reducing atmospheric moisture availability for rainfall (Schott et al., 2009).

BLT: - In the BoB, BLT evolves seasonally with a spring minimum (April–May), late-winter maximum (January–February), and a summer–early winter transition (June–December). A thick BLT insulates the surface from cooler thermocline waters, sustaining warm SSTs and enhancing monsoon rainfall (Thadathil et al., 2007). BLT remains very shallow throughout the year in AS than BoB. The BLT in AS features annual maxima during late winter and remains shallow rest of the year; the shallow BLT is insufficient to significantly alter SST or precipitation (Shenoi et al., 2002). The seasonal cycle of BLT is driven by forcing mechanism of MLD and ILD variability (ILD is controlled by Ekman pumping, net surface heating and propagating long waves. MLD is forced by transfer of turbulent fluxes of heat, mass, and momentum and surface circulations) (Thadathil et al., 2007).

Fig 1: Annual cycle of SSS, SST, Precipitation, MLD and BLT averaged over BoB and AS, depicted using weekly climatology (53 weeks)

Conclusion

The seasonal evolution of most parameters is broadly similar across the two basins, but there is a large difference in the seasonal cycle of SSS, driven by freshwater input and surface circulation (Shenoi et al., 2002). In the BoB, low SSS combined with a shallow MLD and a thick BLT result in strong upper-ocean stratification that traps heat and moisture. This stability maintains SSTs above the convective threshold, supporting intense and prolonged precipitation. In contrast, the AS is characterized by higher salinity, a deeper MLD, a thinner BLT, and stronger wind-driven mixing (Thadathil et al., 2007), which together promote cooler SSTs and consequently weaker precipitation. The stark contrast between the stratified BoB and the well-mixed AS underscores the critical role of upper-ocean processes in modulating monsoon precipitation.

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Conventional Observation Reanalysis (CORe) Datasets

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Introduction

The Conventional Observation Reanalysis (CORe, Ebisuzaki et al., 2020) is planned to become an operational system at the National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) in the calendar year of 2025. It is intended to replace the long-running NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis (Kalnay et al., 1996), which is currently used by the Climate Prediction Center (CPC) at NCEP for real-time climate monitoring. CORe is a global atmospheric reanalysis covering the period from 1950 to the present. It's designed specifically to get better long-term consistency and trends by assimilating only conventional (in situ) observations and Atmospheric Motion Vectors (AMVs). This focus supports CPC's climate monitoring activities.

Data Assimilation System

CORe uses an Ensemble Kalman Filter, specifically the Local Ensemble Transform Kalman Filter (LETKF). The system has an ensemble of 80 members and uses incremental updates. For the forecast model, CORe uses a C128, 64 level cubed sphere model (FV3GFS, v15) with an approximate resolution of 0.7 degrees. A unique feature of CORe among reanalyses is its use of a non-hydrostatic model, which may improve the atmospheric representation of certain physical processes such as breaking gravity waves.

Results

The top panel of Figure 1 shows global temperature anomaly from CORe as a function of pressure (1000 hPa to 10 hPa, y-axis) and year (x-axis), relative to the 1991-2020 climatology. The troposphere exhibits a gradual warming trend, while the stratosphere shows a gradual cooling trend. The warm spikes in the stratosphere correspond to effects of volcanic eruptions which increase the stratospheric aerosols. The middle panel is the same as the top panel except for the JRA-3Q reanalysis (Kosaka et al, 2024), and the bottom panel for ERA-5 (Hersbach et al., 2020). All three reanalyses display quite similar trends, with JRA-3Q exhibiting slightly smaller stratospheric warming from the volcanoes. These comparisons demonstrate a high level of agreement among the latest reanalyses.

Figure 1. Global temperature anomalies for CORe, JRA-3Q and ERA-5.

Figure 2. 10S-10N precipitation anomalies for DYNAMO period for observations, R1, R2, CFSR and CORe.

Figure 2 displays the 10°S-10°N precipitation anomalies during the Dynamics of the MJO (DYNAMO) campaign period from (a) observations (Xie et al., 2017), (b) NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis (R1), (c) NCEP/DOE Reanalysis (R2, Kanamitsu et al., 2002), (d) Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR, Saha et al., 2010) and (e) CORE. Notably, CORE, despite not using satellite radiance data, successfully captures the Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO) precipitation signal over the Indian and Western Pacific Oceans, while the older R1 and R2 systems, despite assimilating satellite retrievals, show weaker MJO signals.

Datasets

The primary CORE data archive contains ensemble means of the atmospheric and land surface state. The analyses are on pressure-level, model levels and special layers. These data are in GRIB version 2 (grib2) format on a 512x256 Gaussian grid which is the data assimilation grid. The secondary level archive includes ensemble members and statistics as well as the observation increments and a subset of model restart files. These files are in grib2, NEMSIO or NetCDF formats.

Cloud Archive

The main distribution of [CORE analyses](#) will be via the NOAA Open Data Dissemination ([NODD](#)) cloud platform. The full archive will eventually cover January 1950 to present with a 2-3 day latency. As of September 2025, the archive includes data from January 1950 to December 2021. Available products include 3-hourly, daily and monthly ensemble mean analyses.

The archive is expected to expand after CORE becomes operational. These datasets are in grib2 format, and conversion to other grids can be easily done using programs, such as [wgrib2](#), and [pygrib](#).

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Numerical/ computational techniques and model resolution, physics-dynamics and physics-physics cross- component coupling

Development of Regional Short-range Prediction Systems Based on KIM

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1. Development of short-range prediction systems based on KIM

The Korean Integrated Model (KIM) was originally designed for the global medium-range forecast. Since its adoption as the operational weather prediction model of the Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA), the Korea Institute of Atmospheric Prediction Systems (KIAPS) has expanded its applications to support seamless prediction across scales. A recent advancement is the development of short-range prediction systems by implementing two model functionalities: the variable-resolution grid system and the limited-area model (LAM) configuration. These short-range prediction systems share core components with the global uniform-resolution KIM, including the non-hydrostatic dynamic core which utilizes the spectral element method on a cubed-sphere grid and the scale-aware physics.

1.1 Variable Resolution grid

The variable-resolution version of KIM was developed using the Schmidt transformation, with increasing horizontal resolutions around the target area. The cubed-sphere framework was extended through an updated transformation matrix, and the time step and numerical viscosity coefficients were adjusted to maintain consistent numerical behavior across resolutions. The degree of grid system deformation is controlled by a stretching factor, S , relative to a reference uniform-resolution grid ($S=1$). Because explicit time integration schemes are limited by the smallest grid spacing, the time step is proportionally reduced by a factor of $1/S$. Evaluation results indicate that the variable-resolution KIM provides forecast skill comparable to high-resolution uniform-grid simulations within the targeted domain and significantly outperforms lower-resolution simulations. Figure 1 illustrates various grid configurations of stretched global grids with different S factors.

1.2 Limited Area Model

The limited-area (regional) version of KIM was developed by constructing a modelling framework that allows the model to operate on a single panel of the cubed sphere. Because the LAM configuration can be employed with the variable-resolution grid system, our “single-panel” approach is able to narrow the LAM domain by setting the stretching factor $S>1$. Figure 1 illustrates the domains with different S values. Lateral boundary conditions are specified at all Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre (GLL) points of the outermost elements and are derived through spatial and temporal interpolation from coarser-resolution global KIM simulations. To enhance simulation stability, a relaxation (or nudging) term is applied near the domain boundaries. This term gradually blends the regional model solution toward the background field and follows the same functional form used in WRF and MPAS.

2. Semi-real time operation and performance

The latest upgrade of KIAPS KIM includes utilities for two regional-scale prediction systems. KIAPS has initiated the internal semi-real-time testing for two short-range prediction systems: (1) a variable-resolution global grid targeting a 3 km resolution over East Asia ($NE^1=576$, $S=2.5$), and (2) a limited-area grid targeting

¹ Number of elements in each panel of the cubed-sphere. Each element has 3×3 GLL grid points for all model configurations mentioned here.

a 1 km resolution over the Korean Peninsula (NE=768, S=5.0). These systems operate in parallel with the global medium-range forecast system with uniform 8-km resolution grid (NE=576) which provides initial and boundary conditions for the two short-range prediction systems. All three systems share the same physics, supporting scale-aware features like convection schemes and gravity wave drag parameterizations. Note that all configurations use the same vertical discretization and resolution. The two short-range prediction systems do not have data assimilation systems, but the 8 km background fields provide observational information.

Preliminary evaluations during the summer monsoon season show that the very-high-resolution systems capture intense precipitation signals for heavy rainfall events, closely matching observations. This highlights the potential of regional ~km resolution systems for reliable forecasting and seamless predictions using KIM (Fig. 2). These developments are set to be integrated into operational systems at KMA following the completion of the second KIAPS project (2020–2026).

Figure 1: Various grid systems in KIM: Global uniform (left), stretched (center), and limited-area grid (right)

Figure 2: 6-h accumulated precipitation (+12-h prediction) simulated by various KIM configurations at 0000 UTC on July 17 2025. Results include simulations from the uniform global 8 km grid (NE576), the global variable-resolution model (NE576S2.5), and the 1 km LAM (NE767S5.0) alongside gauge observation (leftmost).

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Machine learning and AI in weather prediction and climate modeling

Assessment of Regional Acidification and its Amplitude Variability in the Indian Ocean Using an Improved ML-Based Surface pCO₂ Data Product

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Section 1 Background

In recent decades, the Indian Ocean (IO) has experienced significant changes driven by anthropogenic activities, leading to altered biogeochemical properties and increased stress on its marine ecosystems. Accelerated warming, declining oxygen levels, and progressing ocean acidification have made the IO and its coastal regions particularly vulnerable, triggering cascading effects on ecosystem functioning and biogeochemical cycles. To enhance understanding and provide robust climate information, the Ministry of Earth Sciences of the Government of India launched the Deep Ocean Mission. Under this mission, the Ocean Climate Change Advisory Services (OCCAS) deliver long-term projections of essential climate variables. While the surface waters of the Indian Ocean have been undergoing acidification, the variations in the intensity of ocean acidification across different sub-regions remain poorly documented. Such changes in acidification amplitude can exert substantial stress on ocean ecosystems and fisheries (Landschützer et al., 2018). To better analyze past surface [H⁺] variability, we developed an improved long-term partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂) data product by integrating model simulations with available observations using machine learning methods (Ghoshal et al., 2025).

Section 2 Development of Improved pCO₂ Data Product and Regional [H⁺] Analysis

This improved data product built from INCOIS's ocean-ecosystem model outputs (1980-2019) and was developed using an innovative hybrid approach. A machine learning algorithm was applied to correct high-resolution (1/12°) coupled model outputs with observational data from SOCAT (1984-2019) and Indian scientific expeditions (1991-2019) (Ghoshal et al., 2025). The comparison with moored observations and other data products, including CMEMS-LSCE-FFNN and OceanSODA, indicated an improvement of approximately 40% ± 3.31% in RMSE.

Using this improved surface pCO₂ dataset, we calculated [H⁺] (nmol/kg) with the CO₂SYST program. We then determined the annual amplitudes of [H⁺] for the Arabian Sea (AS: 0–30°N, 30–78°E), Bay of Bengal (BoB: 0–30°N, 78–120°E), Equatorial Indian Ocean (EIO: 0–18°S, 30–120°E), and Southern Indian Ocean (SIO: 30–18°S, 30–120°E). Additionally, we computed the linear trends of [H⁺] amplitudes in each region to quantify their amplification or attenuation over time.

Section 3 Regional Patterns of Acidification in the Indian Ocean

Before assessing the rate of change in [H⁺] amplitudes, we first analyzed the rate of change in mean [H⁺] for each sub-region of the Indian Ocean (IO). All sub-regions exhibited a positive rate of change, indicating ongoing ocean acidification across the IO. The highest acidification was observed in the Southern Indian Ocean (SIO: 0.246 ± 0.005 nmol/kg/dec, p < 0.1), while the lowest rate occurred in the Bay of Bengal (BoB: 0.213 ± 0.006 nmol/kg/dec, p < 0.1).

Figure 1: The interannual changes in the $[H^+]$ (acidification) amplitude in the four sub-regions of the IO region. The dashed magenta line shows the linear fit indicating linear trend in each sub-region.

The annual variations in $[H^+]$ amplitudes for each IO sub-region are shown in Figure 1. While SIO exhibits the highest rate of mean acidification, the corresponding $[H^+]$ amplitude shows only a negligible increase (Figure 1d). In contrast, EIO displays the largest amplification of $[H^+]$ amplitudes, with a rate of 0.013 ± 0.004 nmol/kg/dec (Figure 1c). Although mean acidification increases in AS, $[H^+]$ amplitudes there show attenuation (Figure 1a), with a significant decline rate of -0.018 ± 0.005 nmol/kg/dec. However, the interannual variability of $[H^+]$ amplitudes in AS does not follow a consistent linear trend from 1980 to 2019, decreasing until 2000 and then increasing from 2000 to 2019.

This analysis indicates that, although mean $[H^+]$ shows a pronounced increase across the IO, the $[H^+]$ amplitude can either attenuate or amplify depending on regional oceanographic characteristics. AS, known for its strong upwelling, brings dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) to the surface, enhancing surface acidification. However, climate-driven weakening of wind-driven upwelling, combined with increasing anthropogenic stress, can lead to either attenuation or amplification of $[H^+]$ amplitudes. Further investigation of changes in the amplitudes of acidification drivers may help explain the attenuation of $[H^+]$ in AS and its amplification in other sub-regions of IO.

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High resolution rainfall predictions over the Indian region through hybrid integration of dynamical and artificial intelligence models

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1. Rainfall prediction

1.1 Retrospective cases

Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) rainfall is largely contributed by synoptic-scale low-pressure systems over the Bay of Bengal and moves towards the Indian landmass through eastern Indian states such as Odisha. Predicting heavy rainfall events (HREs) at the district scale with adequate lead time (up to 96hours) is a huge challenge for traditional physics-based state-of-the-art high-resolution weather models for complex terrains states like Assam. Hence, for the first time, these studies has used artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) methods to improve the rainfall forecast in retrospective and real time using start of art Weather Research and Forecast (WRF) high resolution (3km) with lead time forecasts (up to 96hour/day4) outputs at the district scale over Odisha (Trivedi et al. 2024a, Sharma et al. 2024) and hilly state Assam (Sharma et al. 2023, Trivedi et al. 2024b).

This pioneering study over the state of Assam, has found that the traditional model has an accuracy skill of 38% compared to 78% for the AI-based model, with a lead of up to 96 hours/ 4 days, at a district scale for heavy rainfall (> 100 mm/day). These skills have been further enhanced by the introduction of a spatio-attention-based AI model over the same study region, i.e., Assam, where the AI-based model achieved the skills of 91.1%. This is the first such type of hybrid model developed in the community (Sharma et al. 2023). The study used deep learning models, specifically a spatial attention-based U-Net, to enhance district-scale rainfall predictions in Assam by utilizing simulated daily rainfall data. The proposed model performed better than both individual and ensemble-based WRF model outputs in June 2022, with a mean absolute error (MAE) of less than 10 mm in rainfall forecasting at the district level for the first time. Furthermore, it is 51.3% more accurate in predicting rainfall categories, achieving 91.9% accuracy compared to the traditional WRF model. The AI/ML model also effectively identified severe rainfall events in districts like Barpeta and Kamrup, while WRF models often underestimated rainfall. (Fig.1). Similarly, for the state of Odisha (Trivedi et al. 2024a), the confusion matrices are utilized to evaluate the rainfall prediction skill of schemes (64-68%) and employed ML (63-70%) and ANN approaches (79-82%). Furthermore, CNN shows promising results with more than 80% percent accuracy in forecasting accurate rainfall for heavy rainfall events at the district scale. On average, DL rainfall forecast skill is 14% and 16% improved compared to ML and WRF models. The inclusion of DL models in the Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) model forecast output convincingly enhances the prediction skills. The ML/DL technique has the benefit of maintaining this spatial discontinuity of rainfall data without any loss in intensity when applied to WRF output forecast data, and this is highly significant in terms of real-time application.

1.2 Real Time cases

A new deep learning (DL) model (kernelized spatial attention-based U-Net) has shown better performance than the WRF model for rainfall prediction up to 96 hours in advance. This DL model reduced the mean absolute error in predictions for two real-time (one MD and another low-pressure) cases in Odisha.

Figure.1: Day 2 (48hour) accumulated rainfall for Kamrup district of Assam for ensemble scheme with their respective U-Net models output and IMD (m). (Trivedi et al. 2024b)

The findings enhance early warning systems, improving preparedness for intense rainfall hazards. The new kernel-based spatial attention models lowered the mean absolute error by 8 mm in Odisha, outperforming WRF (Sharma et al. 2024).

Predicting HREs is challenging for meteorological agencies, especially in areas like Assam. This study simulated an HRE from June 13 to 17, 2023, which has caused severe flooding in Assam in real time for the first time (Trivedi et al. 2024c). To improve rainfall prediction, researchers adopted hybrid approach i.e. using the WRF with a DL model. The DL model showed better accuracy at 54.4%, compared to WRF's 22.8%. It also had a lower MAE of under 30 mm (96hours lead time), effectively capturing rainfall intensity and magnitude in Assam's western and southern regions This research is the first to adopt this model at the district level. The study has found that heavy rainfall category AI (traditional model) forecast accuracy is 85.7% (52.5%), and for very heavy rainfall, it is 87% (56.8%) at the district scale with a lead time up to day-4 (96hours).

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An SPI-SVM Approach for Early Warning of Rainfall Extremes: Demonstration over a Regional Testbed

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Introduction

Heavy precipitation events are increasing globally and, presenting a significant challenge to early warning systems and climate risk management (Center for Climate and Energy Solutions (C2ES)). Regardless, predicting extreme rainfall accumulations continues to be a challenging task because precipitation is very complex and variable and is dependent on numerous factors such as climate variability, local topography, atmospheric circulation, ocean currents, solar activity, human activities (Zhang et al., 2018). Given the intrinsic unpredictability and variability of rainfall across diverse climate regimes, conventional forecasting methods often fall short, thus demanding the adoption of sophisticated modeling approaches capable of capturing these intricate processes more accurately (Sham et al., 2025). Traditional relief and subsidy programs have often been reactive and fiscally burdensome (Mahapatra & Samal, 2024), and these limitations highlight the need for proactive, data-driven approaches. In recent years, Machine Learning (ML) techniques have emerged as valuable instruments in climatology, significantly boosting prediction accuracy and uncovering intricate patterns because of their inherent capacity to handle massive, complex data sets (Lv et al., 2024). Consequently, the present research develops a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model using the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI), specifically leveraging SPI values from varied time scales to characterize rainfall variability. These indices function as the input predictors for the SVM, enabling the model to effectively delineate drought conditions and evaluate rainfall-associated extremes. The methodology is illustrated using a 30-year historical rainfall record sourced from Odisha, an eastern coastal state of India.

Methodological Focus

This study demonstrates a thorough methodology for examining extreme rainfall occurrences by integrating a ML technique. Among different ML methods, SVM is favoured for classification because it successfully identifies a global optimum, reduces overfitting, and preserves high accuracy despite noisy or intricate data. SPI values at multiple accumulation periods are used as predictors within a SVM model. The study explores how methodological choices including SPI timescale selection and SVM kernel configuration influence predictive performance. This approach emphasizes identifying patterns and best practices, providing a transferable, data-driven workflow for analyzing rainfall extremes.

Demonstration Case

To illustrate the methodological approach, the SPI-SVM workflow was applied to a 30-year daily precipitation dataset from Odisha, India. SPI values were calculated at multiple accumulation periods i.e., 3, 6, 12, 18, 24, 36, 48, and 60 months representing short, medium, and long-term rainfall variability. These SPI values were used as input features in a SVM model. The SVM analysis included testing various kernel functions i.e., linear, polynomial, and radial basis function (RBF) to evaluate their influence on model configuration. Model performance was assessed using standard error metrics and classification accuracy. This demonstration serves solely as a proof-of-concept, emphasizing how methodological choices can be applied in practice, while the main contribution lies in the approach and its transferability to other rainfall-affected regions.

Results

The SVM models based on SPI values at different time horizons demonstrated strong predictive skill overall. Most timescales, particularly SPI-6m, SPI-18m, SPI-24m, SPI-36m, SPI-48m, and SPI-60m, achieved high $R^2 > 0.85$ along with low Mean Squared Error ($MSE < 0.13$) and Mean Absolute Error ($MAE < 0.25$), emphasizing the robustness of the approach. A notable deviation was observed for SPI-12m, where the initial performance was relatively weaker ($R^2 \approx 0.63$ in testing) accompanied by the highest errors in the study (MSE of 0.22 and MAE of 0.32 in testing). To address this, kernel optimization was employed, and the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel outperformed linear and polynomial kernels consistently, raising the reliability of SPI-12m predictions.

Complementing this regression-style evaluation, a classification exercise was performed using drought categories derived from SPI-12 values. In this demonstration, the SVM model with an RBF kernel achieved an overall accuracy of 88%. As shown in the classification report bar chart (Figure 1), the model showed balanced precision, recall, and F1-scores across most classes. For example, the model achieved a perfect recall of 1.00 for the Moderately Wet class (Class 4), indicating that all events from that category were correctly identified. The only exception was the extremely wet class (Class 6), which had a support of only 1 sample, leading to a recall and precision of 0.00.

Taken together, these results show the SPI-SVM integration captures rainfall variability across many timescales. The approach is also adaptable to weaker predictive horizons, as demonstrated by the kernel optimization on the SPI-12m timescale to improve its reliability. This robustness of the SVM approach is the study's key contribution, highlighting its potential for use in other rainfall-dependent regions globally, regardless of specific geography.

Figure 1. SVM Classification Metrics by Class (SPI-12)

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Application of artificial intelligence models in improving the intensity forecast of Tropical Cyclones over North Indian Ocean Basin

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1. Tropical Cyclone Intensity

1.1 Estimation

Tropical cyclones (TC) pose serious risks and inflict major property and human damage; comprehending a TC's various stages is crucial to assessing its effects. It has been more challenging but essential in recent years to create effective, high-performing techniques for cyclonic storm prediction, mitigation, and coexistence. In general, it is extremely difficult for operational agencies to estimate the intensity of TC using physics-based dynamical models, and the situation is highly challenging if a TC goes through a Rapid Intensification (RI) phase.

We design a novel attention mechanism for cyclone intensity estimation based on the perceptual Mach band effect that facilitates boosting and suppression of edges in the input image. This is the first work to establish a useful connection between the perceptual Mach band effect and the adaptive feature weighing mechanism intrinsic to the attention model deployed within a deep convolutional neural network (CNN). The Mach band attention model (MBAM) aims to amplify or suppress the prominence of feature locations within the convolutional feature space by leveraging attention weights. We trained and tested our model using INSAT-3DR satellite images and India Meteorological Department (IMD) best intensity archive datasets. The proposed model shows the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.354 (kts) and Root Mean Square Error of 0.415 kts in wind speed estimation. In the cyclone severity classification, the model shows accuracy of 0.9944, recall of 0.9943, and F1-score of 0.9938 shows the excellence of model performance in cyclone's intensity estimation over NIO region (Bansal et al., 2024).

Further, the model has been tested for RI of TCs in NIO basins. The testing of the RI TCs (i.e., Bulbul, Maha, and Nilofar) has been carried out using various attention mechanisms, such as Mach Band and CBAM, with a basic model as ResNet18. The results suggested that the MBAM3 shows the least (2.87 kts) and CBAM4 shows the highest (3.39 kts) RMSE for all TCs. Further, the MBAM3 model is used for RI estimation of the TC. The MBAM model captures the RI phase of the TCs accurately with an RMSE of 1.65 kts for Bulbul, 2.63 kts for Maha, and 1.68 kts for Nilofar (Sharma et al., 2025a).

Figure 1. Actual (obs) and Estimated (model) intensity plot for the TC Nilofar (Sharma et al. 2025).

1.2 Prediction

We have designed a fused deep learning (DL) network comprised of a Vision Transformer (ViT) and Convolutional Block Attention Model (CBAM) with ResNet, known as HASTVi, for cyclone intensity forecast with a lead time of up to 24 hours. The model has been trained and tested using infrared satellite images obtained from the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) and the India Meteorological Department (IMD) best estimates of TC intensity. A total of 38 TCs were used to train and test the model, out of which 35 TCs (7274 images) were used for training and 3 TCs (694 images) were used for testing purposes. The three most devastating TCs, viz. Amphan (2020), Fani (2019), and Tauktae (2021) were used for testing purposes due to their immense socio economic impact. The proposed vision HASTVi model shows the Mean absolute error (MAE) of 2.90 kts, 3.14 kts, and 5.38 kts, for 3hr forecast, which is better than the state-of-the-art Convolutional Long Short Term Memory (ConvLSTM) model, having an MAE of 15.35 kts, 18.99 kts, and 29.90 kts for Taukate, Fani, and Amphan, respectively. In addition, the HASTVi model has been tested for the rapid intensification phase of the TC over the NIO basin (Sharma et al., 2025b). These findings have direct implications for improving the TC early warning systems over the NIO basins.

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